

Concatenation-Type Selfie Numbers With Factorial and Square-Root¹

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Abstract

Numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations are considered as *selfie numbers*. Some times they are called as *wild narcissistic numbers*. There are many ways of representing *selfie numbers*. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with *factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, s-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers, etc.* In this work, we have written *selfie numbers* by use of *concatenation, along with factorial and square-root*. The concatenation idea is used in a very simple way. The work is limited to 5-digits numbers. Work on higher digits shall be dealt elsewhere.

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¹This work is reorganized version of author's previous work <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a138.pdf> [30] done in 2017.

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1 Crazy Representations

In [24], author wrote number from 1 to 11111 in increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. By use of **basic operations**, we got all numbers except 10958 in the increasing case. We can write it by use of factorial and/or square-root. See below:

$$10958 := 1 + 2 + 3!! + (-4 + 5! + 6 - 7) \times 89$$

$$10958 := 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9)$$

For more solutions refer [5, 6, 7] Moreover, this work appeared as improbable research [1, 2, 3, 4]. For more details refers author's link [25].

Recently, Matt Parker [10, 11, 12] gave a new idea of finding this number by using **concatenation** among numbers. See below:

$$10958 := 1 \times 23 + ((4 \times 5 \times 6) || 7 + 8) \times 9,$$

where

$$a || b := 10 \times a + b, a \in \mathbf{Z}, b \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9\}. \tag{1}$$

The notation " || " is known as **concatenation**. More on it can be seen in [9]. The number 23 can also be written as 2||3, but it don't make any effect on the representation.

From *mathematical point of view* the study of concatenation as operator is very deep. For details see [9]. Some general idea can be see at [13, 22]. Some times it is called as **Triangles of the Gods** [23] given below:

1
 1 2
 1 2 3
 1 2 3 4
 1 2 3 4 5
 1 2 3 4 5 6
 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

Remark 1.1. *Our aim here is not to go much deep. Only to work with basic idea, i.e., $10 \times a + b$, where a and b are integers, with condition that b is only of single digit. Let us see below some examples,*

$$2 || 3 := 2 \times 10 + 3 = 23$$

$$(2 + 3) || 5 := (2 + 3) \times 10 + 5 = 55$$

$$(5 \times 4 + 7) \parallel (2 + 3) := 27 \times 10 + 5 = 275.$$

Here we should observe that, in case of real concatenation, when the second component of the pair is of two digits, then the first one is automatically of two digits, i.e., it become as $5 \parallel (7 + 8) = 5 \parallel 15 = 5 \times 100 + 15 = 515$. Another example, $1 \parallel 23 := 100 + 23 = 123$. In this case we can say that $5 \parallel 15 = 51 \parallel 5$, $1 \parallel 23 = 12 \parallel 3$. This type of situation is still not under study. In another opportunity, we shall work with general case of concatenation.

Based on above details we shall bring selfie numbers. First, below is an idea of **selfie numbers** with examples.

1.1 Selfie Numbers

Numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations are considered as "**selfie numbers**". Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. There are many ways of representing "**selfie numbers**". They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial**, **square-root**, **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, **binomial coefficients**, **s-gonal values**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc. Below are some examples with **factorial** and **square-root** written in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and its reverse:

$$\begin{aligned} 936 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! &&= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\ 1296 &:= \sqrt{(1+2)!^9 / 6} &&= 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)} \\ 2896 &:= 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) &&= (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\ 331779 &:= 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} &&= \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\ 342995 &:= (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 &&= -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\ 759375 &:= (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 &&= (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7} \\ 759381 &:= 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 &&= -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7 \end{aligned}$$

More details of **selfie numbers** in different situations are given as summary in last section 4.

In this work our aim is to bring **selfie numbers** by use of **concatenation**, along with **factorial** and **square-root**. The work is limited up to 5 digits. Study for higher digits shall be dealt elsewhere.

2 Concatenation-Type Selfie Numbers

This section brings the selfie numbers by use of formula (1) with factorial and square-root. It has been divided in small subsections according to each type of situation. Before starting there are few numbers those can be written without use of factorial and square-root. See below:

- **Digit's Order**

$$\begin{aligned} 15129 &:= \langle (-1 + 5) \parallel 1 \rangle^2 \times 9 \\ 33124 &:= \langle (3 \times 3) \parallel 1 \rangle^2 \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

- **Reverse Order of Digits**

$$1255 := 5 \times \langle 5^2 \parallel 1 \rangle$$

$$1288 := 8 \times \langle (8 \times 2) \parallel 1 \rangle$$

$$1359 := 9 \times \langle (5 \times 3) \parallel 1 \rangle$$

$$1449 := 9 \times \langle (4 \times 4) \parallel 1 \rangle$$

$$15477 := 77 \times \langle (4 \times 5) \parallel 1 \rangle$$

$$24964 := (4 + \langle (6 + 9) \parallel 4 \rangle)^2$$

$$26896 := (\langle (6 + 9) \parallel 8 \rangle + 6)^2$$

$$39304 := (\langle 4 \parallel 03 \rangle - 9)^3$$

2.1 Sequential Representations

There are many numbers those can be written in sequential way, i.e., from 0 to 9 they have symmetric consecutive representations. Again we have divided it in three part. First one both ways, second one in digit's order and third one in reverse order of digits.

2.1.1 Both Ways

$$30960 := \langle (3 + 0!) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \parallel 3 \rangle$$

$$30961 := \langle (3 + 0!) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \parallel 3 \rangle$$

$$30962 := \langle (3 + 0!) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \parallel 3 \rangle$$

$$30963 := \langle (3 + 0!) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \parallel 3 \rangle$$

$$30964 := \langle (3 + 0!) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \parallel 3 \rangle$$

$$30965 := \langle (3 + 0!) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \parallel 3 \rangle$$

$$30966 := \langle (3 + 0!) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \parallel 3 \rangle$$

$$30967 := \langle (3 + 0!) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \parallel 3 \rangle$$

$$30968 := \langle (3 + 0!) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \parallel 3 \rangle$$

$$30969 := \langle (3 + 0!) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \parallel 3 \rangle$$

2.1.2 Digit's Order

$$37440 := 3!! \times \langle (7 - \sqrt{4}) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 0$$

$$37441 := 3!! \times \langle (7 - \sqrt{4}) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 1$$

$$37442 := 3!! \times \langle (7 - \sqrt{4}) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 2$$

$$37443 := 3!! \times \langle (7 - \sqrt{4}) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 3$$

$$37444 := 3!! \times \langle (7 - \sqrt{4}) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 4$$

$$37445 := 3!! \times \langle (7 - \sqrt{4}) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 5$$

$$37446 := 3!! \times \langle (7 - \sqrt{4}) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 6$$

$$37447 := 3!! \times \langle (7 - \sqrt{4}) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 7$$

$$37448 := 3!! \times \langle (7 - \sqrt{4}) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 8$$

$$37449 := 3!! \times \langle (7 - \sqrt{4}) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 9$$

$$39840 := -(-3 + 9)! + 8! + \langle 4! \parallel 0 \rangle$$

$$39841 := -(-3 + 9)! + 8! + \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle$$

$$39842 := -(-3 + 9)! + 8! + \langle 4! \parallel 2 \rangle$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39843 &:= -(-3+9)! + 8! + \langle 4! \parallel 3 \rangle \\ 39844 &:= -(-3+9)! + 8! + \langle 4! \parallel 4 \rangle \\ 39845 &:= -(-3+9)! + 8! + \langle 4! \parallel 5 \rangle \\ 39846 &:= -(-3+9)! + 8! + \langle 4! \parallel 6 \rangle \\ 39847 &:= -(-3+9)! + 8! + \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \\ 39848 &:= -(-3+9)! + 8! + \langle 4! \parallel 8 \rangle \\ 39849 &:= -(-3+9)! + 8! + \langle 4! \parallel 9 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40080 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle + 0! + 8! + 0 \\ 40081 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle + 0! + 8! + 1 \\ 40082 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle + 0! + 8! + 2 \\ 40083 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle + 0! + 8! + 3 \\ 40084 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle + 0! + 8! + 4 \\ 40085 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle + 0! + 8! + 5 \\ 40086 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle + 0! + 8! + 6 \\ 40087 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle + 0! + 8! + 7 \\ 40088 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle + 0! + 8! + 8 \\ 40089 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle + 0! + 8! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44640 &:= (4!/4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 0 \\ 44641 &:= (4!/4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 1 \\ 44642 &:= (4!/4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 2 \\ 44643 &:= (4!/4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 3 \\ 44644 &:= (4!/4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 4 \\ 44645 &:= (4!/4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 5 \\ 44646 &:= (4!/4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 6 \\ 44647 &:= (4!/4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 7 \\ 44648 &:= (4!/4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 8 \\ 44649 &:= (4!/4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46690 &:= 4 + 6^6 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0 \rangle \\ 46691 &:= 4 + 6^6 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 1 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46692 &:= 4 + 6^6 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 2 \rangle \\ 46693 &:= 4 + 6^6 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 3 \rangle \\ 46694 &:= 4 + 6^6 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 4 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46695 &:= 4 + 6^6 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 5 \rangle \\ 46696 &:= 4 + 6^6 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 6 \rangle \\ 46697 &:= 4 + 6^6 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 7 \rangle \\ 46698 &:= 4 + 6^6 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 8 \rangle \\ 46699 &:= 4 + 6^6 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 9 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69120 &:= 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel (1+2)! \rangle + 0 \\ 69121 &:= 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel (1+2)! \rangle + 1 \\ 69122 &:= 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel (1+2)! \rangle + 2 \\ 69123 &:= 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel (1+2)! \rangle + 3 \\ 69124 &:= 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel (1+2)! \rangle + 4 \\ 69125 &:= 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel (1+2)! \rangle + 5 \\ 69126 &:= 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel (1+2)! \rangle + 6 \\ 69127 &:= 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel (1+2)! \rangle + 7 \\ 69128 &:= 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel (1+2)! \rangle + 8 \\ 69129 &:= 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel (1+2)! \rangle + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 75840 &:= 7! \times 5!/8 + \langle 4! \parallel 0 \rangle \\ 75841 &:= 7! \times 5!/8 + \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle \\ 75842 &:= 7! \times 5!/8 + \langle 4! \parallel 2 \rangle \\ 75843 &:= 7! \times 5!/8 + \langle 4! \parallel 3 \rangle \\ 75844 &:= 7! \times 5!/8 + \langle 4! \parallel 4 \rangle \\ 75845 &:= 7! \times 5!/8 + \langle 4! \parallel 5 \rangle \\ 75846 &:= 7! \times 5!/8 + \langle 4! \parallel 6 \rangle \\ 75847 &:= 7! \times 5!/8 + \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \\ 75848 &:= 7! \times 5!/8 + \langle 4! \parallel 8 \rangle \\ 75849 &:= 7! \times 5!/8 + \langle 4! \parallel 9 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

2.1.3 Reverse Order of Digits

$$01320 := 0 + (2 + 3)! \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$01321 := 1 + (2 + 3)! \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$01322 := 2 + (2 + 3)! \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$01323 := 3 + (2 + 3)! \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$01324 := 4 + (2 + 3)! \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$01325 := 5 + (2 + 3)! \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$01326 := 6 + (2 + 3)! \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$01327 := 7 + (2 + 3)! \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$01328 := 8 + (2 + 3)! \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$01329 := 9 + (2 + 3)! \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03050 := 0 + 50 \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03051 := 1 + 50 \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03052 := 2 + 50 \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03053 := 3 + 50 \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03054 := 4 + 50 \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03055 := 5 + 50 \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03056 := 6 + 50 \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03057 := 7 + 50 \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03058 := 8 + 50 \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03059 := 9 + 50 \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03720 := 0 + (-2 + 7)! \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03721 := 1 + (-2 + 7)! \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03722 := 2 + (-2 + 7)! \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03723 := 3 + (-2 + 7)! \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03724 := 4 + (-2 + 7)! \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03725 := 5 + (-2 + 7)! \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03726 := 6 + (-2 + 7)! \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03727 := 7 + (-2 + 7)! \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03728 := 8 + (-2 + 7)! \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$03729 := 9 + (-2 + 7)! \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$04790 := 0 - 9 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$04791 := 1 - 9 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$04792 := 2 - 9 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$04793 := 3 - 9 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$04794 := 4 - 9 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$04795 := 5 - 9 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$04796 := 6 - 9 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$04797 := 7 - 9 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$04798 := 8 - 9 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$04799 := 9 - 9 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$21960 := 0 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle / 2$$

$$21961 := 1 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle / 2$$

$$21962 := 2 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle / 2$$

$$21963 := 3 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle / 2$$

$$21964 := 4 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle / 2$$

$$21965 := 5 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle / 2$$

$$21966 := 6 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle / 2$$

$$21967 := 7 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle / 2$$

$$21968 := 8 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle / 2$$

$$21969 := 9 + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle / 2$$

$$45360 := 0 + 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{5+4} \rangle$$

$$45361 := 1 + 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{5+4} \rangle$$

$$45362 := 2 + 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{5+4} \rangle$$

$$45363 := 3 + 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{5+4} \rangle$$

$$45364 := 4 + 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{5+4} \rangle$$

$$45365 := 5 + 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{5+4} \rangle$$

$$45366 := 6 + 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{5+4} \rangle$$

$$45367 := 7 + 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{5+4} \rangle$$

$$45368 := 8 + 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{5+4} \rangle$$

$$45369 := 9 + 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{5+4} \rangle$$

$$84960 := 0 + 6! \times \langle (9 + \sqrt{4}) \parallel 8 \rangle$$

$$84961 := 1 + 6! \times \langle (9 + \sqrt{4}) \parallel 8 \rangle$$

$$84962 := 2 + 6! \times \langle (9 + \sqrt{4}) \parallel 8 \rangle$$

$$84963 := 3 + 6! \times \langle (9 + \sqrt{4}) \parallel 8 \rangle$$

$$84964 := 4 + 6! \times \langle (9 + \sqrt{4}) \parallel 8 \rangle$$

$$\begin{aligned} 84965 &:= 5 + 6! \times \langle (9 + \sqrt{4}) \parallel 8 \rangle \\ 84966 &:= 6 + 6! \times \langle (9 + \sqrt{4}) \parallel 8 \rangle \\ 84967 &:= 7 + 6! \times \langle (9 + \sqrt{4}) \parallel 8 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 84968 &:= 8 + 6! \times \langle (9 + \sqrt{4}) \parallel 8 \rangle \\ 84969 &:= 9 + 6! \times \langle (9 + \sqrt{4}) \parallel 8 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

2.2 Non Sequential Representations

In this subsection, there are numbers those are not in a sequential way as of subsection above. Again, we have divided it in three subsections. One on both ways. Second on digit's order and third on reverse order of digits.

2.2.1 Both Ways

Below are selfie numbers those can be written in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and its reverse. The first three numbers are written in one way as they are palindromes.

$$\begin{aligned} 15851 &:= (1 + 5!) \times \langle (8 + 5) \parallel 1 \rangle \\ 44644 &:= (4!/4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 4 \\ 74347 &:= 7 \times 43 \times \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

$$396 := \langle 3! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times 6 = \langle 6 \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times 3!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10582 &:= \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \times (5! \times 8 + 2) &= (2 + 8 \times 5!) \times \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle \\ 10584 &:= \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \times 5! \times 8 + 4! &= 4! + 8 \times 5! \times \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle \\ 10635 &:= (-\langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle + 6!) \times 3 \times 5 &= 5 \times 3 \times (6! - \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle) \\ 14379 &:= (-1 - \langle 4! \parallel 3! \rangle + 7!) \times \sqrt{9} &= \sqrt{9} \times (7! - 3! - \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle) \\ 15079 &:= -\langle (-1 + 5) \parallel 0! \rangle + 7! \times \sqrt{9} &= \sqrt{9} \times 7! - \langle (-0! + 5) \parallel 1 \rangle \\ 15162 &:= \langle \sqrt{-1 + 5} \parallel 1 \rangle \times (6! + 2) &= (2 + 6!) \times \langle \sqrt{-1 + 5} \parallel 1 \rangle \\ 15696 &:= (-1 + 5)! \times (6! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 6 \rangle) &= (-\langle 6 \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 6!) \times (5 - 1)! \\ 17324 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (-2 + 3!) \rangle \times 71 &= \sqrt{1 + 7!} \times \langle (3! - 2)! \parallel 4 \rangle \\ 17346 &:= \langle (-1 + 7) \parallel 3! \rangle + 4! \times 6! &= 6! \times 4! + \langle 3! \parallel (7 - 1) \rangle \\ 19844 &:= \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times (\langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle - 1) &= \left(1 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) \times \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\ 20147 &:= 7! \times 4 - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle - 2 &= -2 - \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle + 4 \times 7! \\ 23593 &:= \langle 3 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (-5 + 3!!) - 2 &= -2 + (3!! - 5) \times \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 3 \rangle \\ 24964 &:= (4 + \langle (6 + 9) \parallel 4 \rangle)^2 &= (2 + \langle (4! - 9) \parallel 6 \rangle)^{\sqrt{4}} \\ 29789 &:= \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel (8 - 7) \rangle^{\sqrt{9}} - 2 &= -2 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel (-7 + 8) \rangle^{\sqrt{9}} \\ 29793 &:= \langle 3 \parallel (-\langle (\sqrt{9})! + 7 \rangle) \rangle^{\sqrt{9}} + 2 &= 2 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel (7 - (\sqrt{9})!) \rangle^3 \\ 30172 &:= -2 + (7! - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 3! &= 3! \times (-\langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle + 7!) - 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 30174 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (7! - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 3 &= -3 \times (\langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle - 7!) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 30282 &:= \langle \sqrt{2 \times 8} \parallel 2 \rangle \times (0! + 3!!) &= (3!! + 0!) \times \langle \sqrt{2 \times 8} \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 30606 &:= ((6 + 0!)! + \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 3! &= ((3! + 0!)! + \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 6 \\
 30636 &:= (\langle 6 \parallel 3! \rangle + (6 + 0!)!) \times 3! &= ((3! + 0!)! + \langle 6 \parallel 3! \rangle) \times 6 \\
 30897 &:= \langle 3 \parallel \sqrt{0! + 8} \rangle^{\sqrt{9}} - 7! &= -7! + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel \sqrt{8 + 0!} \rangle^3 \\
 34398 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle - 3!!) \times 9 + 8! &= 8! + 9 \times (\langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle - 3!!) \\
 34704 &:= 3! \times \langle 4! \parallel (7 \times 0)! \rangle \times 4! &= \langle 4! \parallel (0 \times 7)! \rangle \times 4! \times 3! \\
 39105 &:= (3!! - 9) \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \times 5 &= 5 \times \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle \times (-9 + 3!!) \\
 39304 &:= (3^9 - \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times \sqrt{4} &= (\langle 4 \parallel 03 \rangle - 9)^3 \\
 39498 &:= -\langle 3 \times 9 \parallel 4 \rangle \times \sqrt{9} + 8! &= 8! - \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times 9 + 3! \\
 39658 &:= \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle - 6! - 5 + 8! &= 8! - 5 + \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle - 3!! \\
 39786 &:= (-\langle 3! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 7!) \times 8 - 6 &= -6 + 8 \times (7! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 3! \rangle) \\
 39789 &:= (-\langle 3! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 7!) \times 8 - \sqrt{9} &= -\sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 3! \rangle) \\
 39792 &:= (-\langle 3! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 7!) \times ((\sqrt{9})! + 2) &= 2^{\sqrt{9}} \times (7! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 3! \rangle) \\
 39879 &:= \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (-87 + (\sqrt{9})!!) &= (\sqrt{9} + 7!/8) \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 3 \rangle \\
 39918 &:= -3! \times (\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 1) + 8! &= 8! - (1 + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle) \times 3! \\
 39942 &:= -\langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (\sqrt{9})! + (4 \times 2)! &= (2 \times 4)! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 3! \\
 39948 &:= -\langle (3 \times \sqrt{9}) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 4 + 8! &= 8! - 4 \times \langle 9 \parallel (9/3) \rangle \\
 40058 &:= -\sqrt{4} \times (\langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle + 5!) + 8! &= 8! - (5! + \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 40078 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle - (0 \times 7)! + 8! &= 8! - \langle (-7 + \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle)! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 40108 &:= -\langle \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel 1 \rangle - 0! + 8! &= 8! - \langle \langle (0! + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 40158 &:= -\langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle - 1 - 5! + 8! &= 8! - \langle (5 + \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 40238 &:= -\langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \times \sqrt{-2 + 3!} + 8! &= 8! - \langle (3! + 2) \parallel \sqrt{04} \rangle \\
 40353 &:= \langle (\sqrt{4} + 0!) \parallel 3 \rangle + (5 + 3)! &= (3 + 5)! + \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle + \sqrt{4} \\
 40362 &:= \langle 4 \parallel \sqrt{0! + 3} \rangle + (6 + 2)! &= (2 + 6)! + \langle (3 + 0!) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 40364 &:= \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle + 3 + (\sqrt{64})! &= (\sqrt{4} + 6)! + \langle (3 + 0!) \parallel 4 \rangle \\
 40378 &:= \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle + 37 + 8! &= 8! - 7 + \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle + 4 \\
 40479 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 4! \times 7 - 9 &= -9 + 7 \times \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 4! \\
 40698 &:= \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \times 6 \times \sqrt{9} + 8! &= 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \times (\langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle + \sqrt{4})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 40998 &:= - \left\langle 4 \parallel \left(\sqrt{0! + \sqrt{9}} \right) \right\rangle + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! &= 8! + (\sqrt{9})!! - \left\langle (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \parallel \sqrt{4} \right\rangle \\
 43533 &:= (-4! + 3!! - 5) \times \langle 3! \parallel 3 \rangle &= \langle 3! \parallel 3 \rangle \times (-5 + 3!! - 4!) \\
 43913 &:= -4 - 3 + \left\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \right\rangle \times 3!! &= \langle 3! \parallel 1 \rangle \times (\sqrt{9})!! - 3 - 4 \\
 43919 &:= \sqrt{4} + 3!! \times \left\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \right\rangle - \sqrt{9} &= \left\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \right\rangle \times (\sqrt{9})!! + 3 - 4 \\
 44164 &:= \langle (4!/4) \parallel 1 \rangle \times (6! + 4) &= \langle (4! - 6) \parallel 1 \rangle \times \langle 4! \parallel 4 \rangle \\
 44398 &:= - \left\langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \right\rangle - 3!! + 9!/8 &= 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \times 3!! - \left\langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \right\rangle \\
 44469 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 4 \rangle / 4 \times (6! + 9) &= \sqrt{9^6} \times \langle 4! \parallel 4 \rangle / 4 \\
 44634 &:= -4!/4 + 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle &= -4 + 3!! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle - \sqrt{4} \\
 44636 &:= -4 + (-4 + \langle 6 \parallel 3! \rangle) \times 6! &= 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel (6 - 4) \rangle - 4 \\
 44642 &:= (4!/4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 2 &= (2 + 4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + \sqrt{4} \\
 44646 &:= (4!/4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 6 &= \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times 6! + \sqrt{4} + 4 \\
 45699 &:= 4! + (5 + 6!) \times \left\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel \sqrt{9} \right\rangle &= \left\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel \sqrt{9} \right\rangle \times (6! + 5) + 4! \\
 46344 &:= \sqrt{4^6} \times 3!! + \langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle &= \langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle + 3!! \times 64 \\
 46693 &:= 4 + 6^6 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 3 \rangle &= \langle 3 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 6^6 + 4 \\
 46944 &:= 4! + 6^{(\sqrt{9})!} + \langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle &= \langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle + (\sqrt{9})!^6 + 4! \\
 46968 &:= -4! + \langle 6 \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times (6! - 8) &= (-8 + 6!) \times \left\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 6 \right\rangle - 4! \\
 47424 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \times 4! \times 2 \times 4 &= 4 \times 2 \times \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \times 4! \\
 49236 &:= \left(4! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 2 \right) \times \langle 3! \parallel 6 \rangle &= \langle 6 \parallel 3! \rangle \times \left(2 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 4! \right) \\
 49923 &:= \left\langle (4 \times \sqrt{9}) \parallel 9 \right\rangle^2 \times 3 &= 3 \times \left\langle (2 \times (\sqrt{9})!) \parallel 9 \right\rangle^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 58444 &:= -5! + \left\langle (8 - 4)! \parallel \sqrt{4} \right\rangle^{\sqrt{4}} &= \left\langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \right\rangle^{\sqrt{-4+8}} - 5! \\
 64944 &:= \left\langle (6 \times 4) \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \right\rangle \times \langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle &= 4! \times (\sqrt{4} + 9) \times \langle 4! \parallel 6 \rangle \\
 66954 &:= -6 + 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{5+4} \rangle &= \left\langle (4 + 5) \parallel \sqrt{9} \right\rangle \times 6! - 6 \\
 66996 &:= 6 \times 6 + \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 6! &= 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 6 \times 6 \\
 71999 &:= 7! - 1 + (\sqrt{9})!! \times \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle &= (\sqrt{9})!! \times \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle - 1 + 7! \\
 77448 &:= 7 \times (7! + \langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle) + 8! &= 8! + (\langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle + 7!) \times 7 \\
 79989 &:= -7 \times \left(\langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 8! \right) + 9! &= 9! - \left(8! + \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \right) \times 7 \\
 80728 &:= \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + 7 + 2 \times 8! &= 8! \times 2 + \langle 7 + 0! \parallel 8 \rangle \\
 80804 &:= (\langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8! + 0!) \times \sqrt{4} &= \sqrt{4} \times (0! + \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!) \\
 85344 &:= \left(\langle 4 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 3!! \right) \times (5! - 8) &= (-8 + 5!) \times \left(3!! + \langle 4 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 93955 &:= \left((\sqrt{9})!! + \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \right) \times 5! - 5 &= -5 + 5! \times \left((\sqrt{9})!! + \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \right) \\
 96624 &:= \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 6 \rangle \times (6! \times 2 + 4!) &= (4! + 2 \times 6!) \times \langle 6 \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \\
 98404 &:= \sqrt{9} + 8! + \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} &= \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} + 8! + \sqrt{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

2.2.2 Digit's Order

Below are selfie numbers written in digit's order. The numbers appearing in subsection 2.2.1 are written again except those given in section on sequential representations 2.1.

$$\begin{aligned}
 305 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 5 & 4920 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times 20 \\
 396 &:= \langle 3! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times 6 & 4937 &:= -\langle 4 + (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 3 \rangle + 7! \\
 473 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle + 3!! & 4997 &:= -\langle 4 \parallel (9/\sqrt{9}) \rangle + 7! \\
 492 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times 2 & 5040 &:= 5! \times (0! + \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 793 &:= \langle 7 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 3!! & 5091 &:= \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle + \left((\sqrt{9})! + 1 \right)! \\
 796 &:= \langle 7 \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 6! & 5097 &:= \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle + (\sqrt{9})! + 7! \\
 & & 5640 &:= 5! \times (6 + \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 & & 9984 &:= -\langle 9 \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 8!/4 \\
 1446 &:= \left(-1 + \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \right) \times 6 & 10285 &:= \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle^2 \times 85 \\
 1476 &:= \left(-1 + \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \right) \times 6 & 10404 &:= \langle 10 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle^{\sqrt{04}} \\
 1489 &:= 1 + \langle 4! \parallel 8 \rangle \times (\sqrt{9})! & 10582 &:= \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \times (5! \times 8 + 2) \\
 1493 &:= -1 + \langle 4! \parallel 9 \rangle \times 3! & 10584 &:= \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \times 5! \times 8 + 4! \\
 1495 &:= \left(-1 + 4! \right) \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 5 \rangle & 10635 &:= \left(-\langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle + 6! \right) \times 3 \times 5 \\
 1920 &:= \left(-1 + 9 \right)! / \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle & 10648 &:= \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle^{6/\sqrt{4}} \times 8 \\
 1968 &:= \langle (1 + \sqrt{9})! \parallel 6 \rangle \times 8 & 10789 &:= -\langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle + (7 + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 2904 &:= \langle 2 \times (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 4! & 12544 &:= \langle (1 + 2 \times 5) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 3050 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 50 & 14056 &:= \langle (1 + 4!) \parallel 0! \rangle \times 56 \\
 3535 &:= 3!! \times 5 - \langle 3! \parallel 5 \rangle & 14091 &:= \langle (-1 + 4!) \parallel 0! \rangle \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 3844 &:= \langle 3! \parallel (8/4) \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} & 14379 &:= \left(-1 - \langle 4! \parallel 3! \rangle + 7! \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 3905 &:= \left(3!! + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \times 5 & 14632 &:= \langle (-1 + 4!) \parallel 6 \rangle \times \langle 3! \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 3955 &:= \langle 3 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 5! - 5 & 14760 &:= \left(-1 + \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \right) \times 60 \\
 3960 &:= \langle 3 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (6 - 0!)! & 14873 &:= 1 - \langle 4! \parallel 8 \rangle + 7! \times 3 \\
 3969 &:= \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle^{6/\sqrt{9}} & 15079 &:= -\langle (-1 + 5) \parallel 0! \rangle + 7! \times \sqrt{9} \\
 4079 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle + 7! - (\sqrt{9})!! & 15129 &:= \langle (-1 + 5) \parallel 1 \rangle^2 \times 9 \\
 4332 &:= -4! + \langle 3! \parallel 3! \rangle^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 15141 &:= (1 + (5 + 1)!) \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 15162 &:= \langle \sqrt{-1 + 5} \parallel 1 \rangle \times (6! + 2) \\
 15367 &:= (1 + 5!) \times \langle (3! + 6) \parallel 7 \rangle \\
 15488 &:= (1 + 5!) \times \langle (4 + 8) \parallel 8 \rangle \\
 15535 &:= (-1 + 5! + 5!) \times \langle 3! \parallel 5 \rangle \\
 15696 &:= (-1 + 5!) \times \left(6! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 6 \rangle \right) \\
 15851 &:= (1 + 5!) \times \langle (8 + 5) \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 15972 &:= (1 + 5!) \times \langle \left((\sqrt{9})! + 7 \right) \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 16896 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{16^8}} \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 6 \rangle \\
 17039 &:= -1 + \langle 7 \parallel 0! \rangle \times 3! / \sqrt{9} \\
 17040 &:= \sqrt{1 + 7!} \times (-0! + \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 17324 &:= \sqrt{1 + 7!} \times \langle (3! - 2)! \parallel 4 \rangle \\
 17329 &:= 1 + \langle 7 \parallel 3! \rangle^2 \times \sqrt{9} \\
 17343 &:= \langle (-1 + 7) \parallel 3 \rangle + 4! \times 3! \\
 17346 &:= \langle (-1 + 7) \parallel 3! \rangle + 4! \times 6! \\
 17424 &:= \langle (17 - 4) \parallel 2 \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 17463 &:= \sqrt{1 + 7!} \times \langle 4! \parallel 6 \rangle - 3 \\
 17464 &:= \sqrt{1 + 7!} \times \langle 4! \parallel 6 \rangle - \sqrt{4} \\
 17466 &:= \sqrt{1 + 7!} \times \langle (4 \times 6) \parallel 6 \rangle \\
 17469 &:= \sqrt{1 + 7!} \times \langle 4! \parallel 6 \rangle + \sqrt{9} \\
 17495 &:= -1 + \langle 7 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times \sqrt{9^5} \\
 17640 &:= 1 \times 7! / 6 \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 17641 &:= 1 + 7! / 6 \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 18504 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{1 + 8} \right)!! + \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \times 4! \\
 18744 &:= \sqrt{1^8 + 7!} \times \langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle \\
 19225 &:= \left(1 + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 2 \rangle^2 \right) \times 5 \\
 19680 &:= \langle (1 + \sqrt{9})! \parallel 6 \rangle \times 80 \\
 19844 &:= \left(1 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 19845 &:= 1 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times \langle 4! \parallel 5 \rangle \\
 20147 &:= -2 - \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle + 4 \times 7! \\
 20182 &:= \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle + 1 + 8! / 2 \\
 20349 &:= \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \times (3! + \langle 4! \parallel 9 \rangle) \\
 20880 &:= (\langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8) \times (\sqrt{8 + 0!})!! \\
 20979 &:= -\langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle^{\sqrt{9}} + 7! \times (\sqrt{9})! \\
 23042 &:= 2 + 3!! \times \langle (0! + \sqrt{4}) \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 23392 &:= (2 + 3^3!) \times \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 23593 &:= -2 + (3!! - 5) \times \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 3 \rangle \\
 24288 &:= 2 \times 4!! / \langle 2 \parallel (8/8) \rangle! \\
 24957 &:= -\langle 24 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 5 \times 7! \\
 24964 &:= (2 + \langle (4! - 9) \parallel 6 \rangle)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 25048 &:= \langle 2 \times 5 \parallel 0! \rangle \times \langle 4! \parallel 8 \rangle \\
 25149 &:= \langle 2 \times 5 \parallel 1 \rangle \times \langle 4! \parallel 9 \rangle \\
 25344 &:= 2^5 \times 3 \times \langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle \\
 25405 &:= ((2 + 5)! + \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 5 \\
 25407 &:= 2 + 5 \times (\langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle + 7!) \\
 25575 &:= (\langle (2 + 5) \parallel 5 \rangle + 7!) \times 5 \\
 26136 &:= \langle (2 \times 6) \parallel 1 \rangle \times \sqrt{3!^6} \\
 27362 &:= 2 + \langle 7 \parallel 3! \rangle \times 6! / 2 \\
 29040 &:= (2 + \sqrt{9})! \times (0! + \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 29042 &:= 2 + \left((\sqrt{9})! - 0! \right)! \times \langle 4! \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 29440 &:= 2 + \left((\sqrt{9})!! - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 29549 &:= 29 + 5! \times \langle 4! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \\
 29640 &:= (2 + \sqrt{9})! \times (6 + \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 29789 &:= -2 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel (-7 + 8) \rangle^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 29793 &:= 2 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel (7 - (\sqrt{9})!) \rangle^3 \\
 29997 &:= -\langle (-2 + (\sqrt{9})!)! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + (\sqrt{9})! \times 7! \\
 30172 &:= 3! \times (-\langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle + 7!) - 2 \\
 30173 &:= -\langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle + (-1 + 7!) \times 3! \\
 30174 &:= -3 \times (\langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle - 7!) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 30179 &:= -\langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle + 1 \times 7! \times (\sqrt{9})! \\
 30264 &:= \langle (3 + 0!) \parallel 2 \rangle \times 6! + 4! \\
 30273 &:= \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle + 2 + 7! \times 3! \\
 30282 &:= (3!! + 0!) \times \langle \sqrt{2 \times 8} \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 30307 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle + 3! \times (0! + 7!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 30337 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle + 3! \times (3! + 7!) \\
 30500 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 500 \\
 30576 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle - 5 + 7!) \times 6 \\
 30606 &:= ((3! + 0!)! + \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 6 \\
 30636 &:= ((3! + 0!)! + \langle 6 \parallel 3! \rangle) \times 6 \\
 30667 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle + 6! \times 6) \times 7 \\
 30866 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \times (\sqrt{86} - 6) \\
 30897 &:= \langle 3 \parallel \sqrt{0! + 8} \rangle^{\sqrt{9}} - 7! \\
 31232 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 1 \rangle \times 2^{3^2} \\
 32830 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 2 \rangle + 8^{(3! - 0!)} \\
 32854 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 2 \rangle + 8^5 + 4! \\
 33044 &:= (3!! + \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 44 \\
 33124 &:= \langle (3 \times 3) \parallel 1 \rangle^2 \times 4 \\
 33327 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel 3 \rangle + 3!)^2 \times 7 \\
 33492 &:= 3 + \langle (-3! + 4!) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle^2 \\
 33589 &:= (-\langle 3! \parallel 3! \rangle + 5 \times 8!) / (\sqrt{9})! \\
 33597 &:= 3^{3!} \times \langle 5 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle - 7! \\
 33696 &:= 3!^3 \times \langle (6 + 9) \parallel 6 \rangle \\
 34398 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle - 3!!) \times 9 + 8! \\
 34495 &:= 3!! \times (4! + 4!) - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 5 \rangle \\
 34496 &:= -\langle 3! \parallel 4 \rangle + 4! \times ((\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) \\
 34624 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 4 \rangle + 6! \times 2 \times 4! \\
 34702 &:= (3!! \times 4! + \langle 7 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 2 \\
 34704 &:= 3! \times \langle 4! \parallel (7 \times 0)! \rangle \times 4! \\
 34937 &:= (3! + \langle 4 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle) \times (3!! - 7) \\
 34944 &:= (3! \times \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle - \sqrt{4}) \times 4! \\
 34972 &:= 3 + \langle (\sqrt{4} \times 9) \parallel 7 \rangle^2 \\
 35939 &:= -3 + 5 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 3 \rangle^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 35964 &:= (3 + 5)! - \left(\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 6 \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 36567 &:= (-3 + 6!) \times \langle 5 \parallel (-6 + 7) \rangle \\
 37560 &:= 3! \times 7! + 5! \times \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 38073 &:= \langle (3 + 8) \parallel 0! \rangle \times 7^3 \\
 38520 &:= 3!! + 8! - 5! \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 39050 &:= (3!! + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 50 \\
 39052 &:= (3!! + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 52 \\
 39105 &:= (3!! - 9) \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \times 5 \\
 39204 &:= (3! \times (\langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 2 \rangle + 0!))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 39228 &:= -3! \times \langle (9 \times 2) \parallel 2 \rangle + 8! \\
 39284 &:= 3^9 \times 2 - \langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 39304 &:= (3^9 - \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 39328 &:= -3!! - \langle (9 \times 3) \parallel 2 \rangle + 8! \\
 39378 &:= -3! \times \langle (9 + 3!) \parallel 7 \rangle + 8! \\
 39435 &:= (3!! - \sqrt{9}) \times \langle (\sqrt{4} + 3) \parallel 5 \rangle \\
 39438 &:= -\langle (3 \times 9) \parallel 4! \rangle \times 3 + 8! \\
 39468 &:= -\langle 3 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 4 - 6! + 8! \\
 39484 &:= -3!! - \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 8! - 4! \\
 39498 &:= -\langle (3 \times 9) \parallel 4 \rangle \times \sqrt{9} + 8! \\
 39508 &:= -3!! - \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{5 - 0!} \rangle + 8! \\
 39535 &:= -3!! + (\sqrt{9} + 5)! - \langle 3! \parallel 5 \rangle \\
 39538 &:= -\langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9 - 5} \rangle - 3!! + 8! \\
 39658 &:= \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle - 6! - 5 + 8! \\
 39690 &:= \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (6! - 90) \\
 39738 &:= -\langle (3 \times \sqrt{9}) \parallel 7 \rangle \times 3! + 8! \\
 39768 &:= (-\langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 7! - 6) \times 8 \\
 39786 &:= (-\langle 3! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 7!) \times 8 - 6 \\
 39789 &:= (-\langle 3! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 7!) \times 8 - \sqrt{9} \\
 39792 &:= (-\langle 3! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 7!) \times ((\sqrt{9})! + 2) \\
 39879 &:= \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (-87 + (\sqrt{9})!!) \\
 39894 &:= -\langle 3! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 8! - (\sqrt{9})!! / \sqrt{4} \\
 39918 &:= -3! \times (\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 1) + 8! \\
 39942 &:= -\langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (\sqrt{9})! + (4 \times 2)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 39948 &:= - \langle (3 \times \sqrt{9}) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 4 + 8! \\
 40058 &:= -\sqrt{4} \times (\langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle + 5!) + 8! \\
 40068 &:= - (\langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle + 0!) \times 6 + 8! \\
 40073 &:= - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle + (0! + 7)! - 3! \\
 40078 &:= - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle - (0 \times 7)! + 8! \\
 40079 &:= - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle + (\sqrt{0! + 7 \times 9})! \\
 40098 &:= - \langle (4! - 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle + 9 + 8! \\
 40108 &:= - \langle \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel 1 \rangle - 0! + 8! \\
 40109 &:= - \langle \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel 1 \rangle + (-0! + 9)! \\
 40158 &:= - \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle - 1 - 5! + 8! \\
 40185 &:= -4 - \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle + 8! + 5! \\
 40238 &:= - \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \times \sqrt{-2 + 3!} + 8! \\
 40247 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \times \langle 2^4 \parallel 7 \rangle \\
 40279 &:= - \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle + (2 + 7)! / 9 \\
 40281 &:= - \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle + 2 + 8! \times 1 \\
 40299 &:= - \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel (0 \times 2)! \rangle + 9! / 9 \\
 40340 &:= \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle + (3! + \sqrt{4})! - 0! \\
 40341 &:= \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle + (3 + 4 + 1)! \\
 40353 &:= \langle (\sqrt{4} + 0!) \parallel 3 \rangle + (5 + 3)! \\
 40358 &:= \langle 4 \parallel 03 \rangle - 5 + 8! \\
 40361 &:= \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle + (3 + 6 - 1)! \\
 40362 &:= \langle 4 \parallel \sqrt{0! + 3} \rangle + (6 + 2)! \\
 40364 &:= \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle + 3 + (\sqrt{64})! \\
 40368 &:= \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle + \sqrt{3^6} + 8! \\
 40378 &:= \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle + 37 + 8! \\
 40428 &:= \langle (4 + 0!) \parallel 4 \rangle \times 2 + 8! \\
 40448 &:= \langle (\sqrt{4} + 0!) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times 4 + 8! \\
 40479 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 4! \times 7 - 9 \\
 40482 &:= \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \times 4 + 8! - 2 \\
 40485 &:= \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle + 4 + 8! + 5! \\
 40535 &:= \langle \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel 5 \rangle + (3 + 5)! \\
 40538 &:= \langle \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel 5 + 3 \rangle + 8! \\
 40564 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (-0! + 5) \rangle + (\sqrt{64})! \\
 40571 &:= \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{0! + 5!} \rangle + (7 + 1)! \\
 40578 &:= \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{0! + 5!} \rangle + 7 + 8! \\
 40588 &:= \langle \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle + 5 \parallel 8 \rangle + 8! \\
 40648 &:= \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \times \sqrt{64} + 8! \\
 40685 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (-0! + 6) \rangle + 8! + 5! \\
 40698 &:= \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \times 6 \times \sqrt{9} + 8! \\
 40783 &:= - \langle (4! + 0!) \parallel 7 \rangle + 8! + 3!! \\
 40948 &:= (\sqrt{4} + 0!)!! - \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 8! \\
 40959 &:= \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \times (-9 + 5!) \times 9 \\
 40998 &:= - \langle 4 \parallel \sqrt{0! + \sqrt{9}} \rangle + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! \\
 40999 &:= - \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle + (\sqrt{9})!! + 9! / 9 \\
 41248 &:= \langle (4! - 1) \parallel 2 \rangle \times 4 + 8! \\
 41283 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (1 + 2) \rangle + 8! + 3!! \\
 41286 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (1 + 2)! \rangle + 8! + 6! \\
 41328 &:= 4! \times \langle (1 + 3) \parallel 2 \rangle + 8! \\
 41493 &:= \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle + 4!^{\sqrt{9}} \times 3 \\
 41637 &:= \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle + 6^{3!} - 7! \\
 41868 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 18 \rangle \times 6 + 8! \\
 41934 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle \times (- (\sqrt{9})! + 3!! / 4) \\
 41984 &:= \sqrt{(4 \times 1)^9} \times \langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 42088 &:= \langle (4! - 2) \parallel 0! \rangle \times 8 + 8! \\
 42498 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (-2 + 4) \rangle \times 9 + 8! \\
 43152 &:= (-4! + 3!!) \times \langle (1 + 5) \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 43248 &:= \langle (4 \times 3) \parallel 2 \rangle \times 4! + 8! \\
 43404 &:= 4! + 3!! \times \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle / 4 \\
 43533 &:= (-4! + 3!! - 5) \times \langle 3! \parallel 3 \rangle \\
 43555 &:= (\langle 4! \parallel 3 \rangle + 5!) \times 5! - 5 \\
 43560 &:= (\langle 4! \parallel 3 \rangle + 5!) \times (6 - 0!)! \\
 43591 &:= -4! + (3!! - 5) \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 43896 &:= -4! + \langle 3! \parallel (-8 + 9) \rangle \times 6! \\
 43908 &:= -4 + 3!! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle - 8 \\
 43909 &:= -\sqrt{4} + 3!! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle - 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43913 &:= -4 - 3 + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle \times 3!! \\
 43914 &:= -4 + 3!! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle - \sqrt{4} \\
 43915 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle - 5 \\
 43916 &:= -4 + \langle (-3 + 9) \parallel 1 \rangle \times 6! \\
 43917 &:= 4 + 3!! \times \langle \sqrt{9}! \parallel 1 \rangle - 7 \\
 43918 &:= -\sqrt{4} + 3!! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1^8 \rangle \\
 43919 &:= \sqrt{4} + 3!! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle - \sqrt{9} \\
 43920 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times \langle (\sqrt{9} \times 2) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 43922 &:= \sqrt{4} + 3!! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel (2/2) \rangle \\
 43924 &:= 4 + 3!! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel (2/\sqrt{4}) \rangle \\
 43930 &:= 4 + 3! + (\sqrt{9})!! \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 43944 &:= 4! + 3!! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel (4/4) \rangle \\
 44164 &:= \langle (4!/4) \parallel 1 \rangle \times (6! + 4) \\
 44392 &:= (-4 + (\sqrt{4} \times 3)!) \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 44394 &:= \sqrt{4} + (-4 + 3!!) \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 44398 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle - 3!! + 9!/8 \\
 44469 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 4 \rangle / 4 \times (6! + 9) \\
 44590 &:= \sqrt{4} \times \langle 4! \parallel 5 \rangle \times \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 44632 &:= -4 - 4 + 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 44634 &:= -4!/4 + 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 44636 &:= -4 + (-4 + \langle 6 \parallel 3! \rangle) \times 6! \\
 45336 &:= (-4 + 5! \times \langle 3! \parallel 3 \rangle) \times 6 \\
 45479 &:= (-\sqrt{4} + 5^4) \times \langle 7 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \\
 45664 &:= 4^5 + 6! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 45699 &:= 4! + (5 + 6!) \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \\
 45835 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 5 \rangle - 8! + 3!! \times 5! \\
 45909 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} + 5)! + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \times 9 \\
 46056 &:= -4! + \langle 6 \parallel (-0! + 5) \rangle \times 6! \\
 46326 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 6 \rangle + 3!! \times 2^6 \\
 46344 &:= \sqrt{4^6} \times 3!! + \langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle \\
 46670 &:= (\sqrt{4} - 6!) \times (6 - \langle 7 \parallel 0! \rangle)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46763 &:= \langle (4 + 6) \parallel 7 \rangle + 6^3! \\
 46902 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 6 \rangle + (\sqrt{9})!^{(0!+2)!} \\
 46930 &:= (\sqrt{4} + 6!) \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel (3! - 0!) \rangle \\
 46944 &:= 4! + 6^{(\sqrt{9})!} + \langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle \\
 46954 &:= (\sqrt{4} + 6!) \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 5 \rangle + 4! \\
 46968 &:= -4! + \langle 6 \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times (6! - 8) \\
 47424 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \times 4! \times 2 \times 4 \\
 47488 &:= (\langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \times 4! + 8) \times 8 \\
 47496 &:= -4! + \langle (7 - 4)! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times 6! \\
 49200 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times 200 \\
 49236 &:= (4! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 2) \times \langle 3! \parallel 6 \rangle \\
 49248 &:= 4! \times 9 \times \langle \langle 2 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \parallel 8 \rangle \\
 49704 &:= 4! - (\sqrt{9})!! \times (-\langle 7 \parallel 0! \rangle + \sqrt{4}) \\
 49790 &:= (4 + (\sqrt{9})!) \times (7! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 49923 &:= \langle (4 \times \sqrt{9}) \parallel 9 \rangle^2 \times 3 \\
 49933 &:= (4 + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle)^3 - 3!! \\
 51984 &:= (5! + \langle (1 + 9) \parallel 8 \rangle)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 53347 &:= -5 + 3!^3 \times \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \\
 53824 &:= \langle (5 \times 3 + 8) \parallel 2 \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 54294 &:= 5 + (\langle 4! \parallel 2 \rangle - 9)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 54590 &:= -5 \times (\sqrt{4} - 5! \times \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 54739 &:= -5 + 4! + \langle 7 \parallel 3! \rangle \times (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 55080 &:= 5! \times \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle \times (8 + 0!) \\
 58035 &:= 5! + \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle \times (3!! - 5) \\
 58320 &:= (-5 + 8)!! \times \langle (3! + 2) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 58444 &:= -5! + \langle (8 - 4)! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 58920 &:= 5! \times (8^{\sqrt{9}} - \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 58968 &:= (-5 + \langle 8 \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle) \times (6! + 8) \\
 59009 &:= (-5! + \sqrt{9^{(0! \parallel 0!)}}) / \sqrt{9} \\
 59045 &:= \langle (-5 + 9)! \parallel 0! \rangle \times \langle 4! \parallel 5 \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 59880 &:= 5! + (\sqrt{9})!! \times \langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{8+0!} \rangle \\
 59926 &:= \langle (5 + \sqrt{9}) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (2 + 6!) \\
 60846 &:= (\langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!/4) \times 6 \\
 61832 &:= (6! - 1) \times \langle 8 \parallel 3! \rangle - 2 \\
 61834 &:= (6! - 1) \times \langle 8 \parallel (3 \times \sqrt{4}) \rangle \\
 61920 &:= 6! \times \langle (-1 + 9) \parallel (2 + 0!)! \rangle \\
 62496 &:= \langle 6 \times 2 \parallel 4 \rangle \times 9!/6! \\
 63084 &:= (6! + \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 84 \\
 63360 &:= 6! \times (-3 + \langle (3 + 6) \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 63888 &:= (6! + 3!) \times \langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{8 \times 8} \rangle \\
 64080 &:= 6! \times (-\sqrt{4} + \langle (0! + 8) \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 64729 &:= (6 + \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle)^2 + (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 64944 &:= \langle 6 \times 4 \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times \langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle \\
 64980 &:= (6! + \sqrt{4}) \times (9 + \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 66954 &:= -6 + 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{5+4} \rangle \\
 66996 &:= 6 \times 6 + \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 6! \\
 68085 &:= (6! + \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 85 \\
 68400 &:= 6! \times (84 + \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 69092 &:= (6! + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 92 \\
 69336 &:= 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel 3! \rangle + \sqrt{3!^6} \\
 69408 &:= 6 \times (\sqrt{9})! \times \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 8 \\
 69435 &:= (\langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 4!^3) \times 5 \\
 69792 &:= (-6 + \sqrt{9^7}) \times \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 71999 &:= 7! - 1 + (\sqrt{9})!! \times \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \\
 72595 &:= (\langle (7 + 2) \parallel 5 \rangle + 9!) / 5 \\
 73435 &:= \langle (7 + 3) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times 3!! - 5 \\
 73439 &:= (-7 + 3!!) \times \langle (4 + 3!) \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \\
 73464 &:= \langle (7 + 3) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times 6! + 4! \\
 74347 &:= 7 \times 43 \times \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \\
 74949 &:= 7 \times \langle 4 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times \langle 4! \parallel 9 \rangle \\
 77448 &:= 7 \times (7! + \langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle) + 8!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 79345 &:= 7 \times 9! / \langle 3 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle - 5 \\
 79524 &:= \langle 7 \times (9 - 5) \parallel 2 \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 79989 &:= -7 \times (\langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 8!) + 9! \\
 80482 &:= (-\langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + \sqrt{4} + 8!) \times 2 \\
 80728 &:= \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + 7 + 2 \times 8! \\
 80802 &:= (\langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!) \times 02 \\
 80804 &:= (\langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8! + 0!) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 80832 &:= (8! + \langle (0! + 8) \parallel 3! \rangle) \times 2 \\
 85344 &:= (-8 + 5!) \times (3!! + \langle 4 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle) \\
 86400 &:= (8! - 6!) \times 4! / \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 89264 &:= (-8 + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 2 \rangle \times 6!) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 89304 &:= 8 \times \sqrt{9} \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 90659 &:= -\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle + 6! \times (5! + (\sqrt{9})!) \\
 90741 &:= (-\langle \sqrt{9} \rangle!! + 0! + 7!) \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 90782 &:= (\langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0! \rangle + 7! + 8!) \times 2 \\
 90846 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! + 0!) \times \langle (8 + 4) \parallel 6 \rangle \\
 91295 &:= \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 1 \rangle^2 \times 95 \\
 92248 &:= \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 2 \rangle^2 \times 4! - 8 \\
 93259 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^{3!} \times 2 - \langle 5 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \\
 93584 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! \times \langle 3! \parallel 5 \rangle - 8) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 93852 &:= (-9 + 3!!) \times \langle (8 + 5) \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 93955 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! + \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle) \times 5! - 5 \\
 93960 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! + \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle) \times (6 - 0!)! \\
 93984 &:= \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 3 \rangle \times ((\sqrt{9})!! - 8) \times 4 \\
 94080 &:= 9! \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle / \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 94089 &:= 9 + \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \times 8! / 9 \\
 94320 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! \times \langle (4 + 3^2) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 96624 &:= \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 6 \rangle \times (6! \times 2 + 4!) \\
 96795 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + 6!) \times \langle 7 + (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 5 \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$97344 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \langle (7+3) \parallel 4 \rangle \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$97920 := \left(\sqrt{9} \right)!! \times \langle 7 + \left(\sqrt{9} \right)! \parallel (2+0!) \rangle$$

$$98404 := \sqrt{9} + 8! + \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$99225 := \left\langle \left(\sqrt{9} \right)! \parallel \sqrt{9} \right\rangle^2 \times 25$$

$$99360 := 9! - \left(\sqrt{9} \right)! \times 3!! \times \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

2.2.3 Reverse Order of Digits

Below are selfie numbers written in reverse order of digits. The numbers appearing in subsection [?] are written again except those given in subsection on sequential representations 2.1.

$$147 := 7 \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle$$

$$241 := -1 + \langle 4! \parallel 2 \rangle$$

$$244 := \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4^2} \rangle$$

$$264 := \langle 4! \parallel (6-2)! \rangle$$

$$396 := \langle 6 \parallel \left(\sqrt{9} \right)! \rangle \times 3!$$

$$0105 := 5 \times \langle (0! + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0109 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \right)! - 0! \right)! - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0122 := 2 \times \langle (2+1)! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0124 := 4 \times \langle (2+1) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0132 := 2 \times 3! \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0182 := 2 \times \langle (8+1) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0183 := 3 \times \langle \left(\sqrt{8+1} \right)! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0186 := 6 \times \langle \sqrt{8+1} \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0201 := \langle 10 \times 2 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0217 := 7 \times \langle (1+2) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0231 := \langle (-1 + (3! - 2)!) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0241 := \langle 1 \times 4! \parallel (2 \times 0)! \rangle$$

$$0243 := \langle (3! \times 4) \parallel 2 \rangle + 0!$$

$$0249 := \left(\sqrt{9} \right)! + \langle 4! \parallel 2 \rangle + 0!$$

$$0251 := \langle (1 \times 5^2) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0261 := \langle \left(\sqrt{16} \right)! \parallel \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \rangle$$

$$0273 := 3 \times \langle (7+2) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0279 := 9 \times \langle \sqrt{7+2} \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0287 := 7 \times \langle (8/2) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0305 := \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle \times 3! - 0!$$

$$0306 := 6 \times \langle (-0! + 3!) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0324 := 4 \times \langle 2^3 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0328 := 8 \times \langle (-2 + 3!) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0329 := \left(\sqrt{9} \right)!! / 2 - \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0357 := 7 \times \langle 5 \parallel (3 \times 0)! \rangle$$

$$0362 := 2 \times \langle (6 \times 3) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0364 := 4 \times \langle (6+3) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0366 := 6 \times \langle 6 \parallel (3 \times 0)! \rangle$$

$$0375 := 5 \times \langle \langle 7 \parallel 3! \rangle - 0! \rangle$$

$$0408 := 8 \times \langle (0! + 4) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0427 := 7 \times \langle (2+4) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0451 := \sqrt{1+5!} \times \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0455 := 5 \times \langle (5+4) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0459 := 9 \times \langle 5 \parallel (4 \times 0)! \rangle$$

$$0482 := 2 \times \langle (8-4)! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0483 := 3 \times \langle (8 \times \sqrt{4}) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0486 := 6 \times \langle 8 \parallel (4 \times 0)! \rangle$$

$$0488 := 8 \times \langle (8 - \sqrt{4}) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0492 := 2 \times \left(\sqrt{9} \right)! \times \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0497 := 7 \times \langle (9 - \sqrt{4}) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0498 := \langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times \left(\sqrt{4} + 0! \right)!$$

$$0504 := \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \times (5 - 0)!!$$

$$0546 := 6 \times \langle (4+5) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0549 := 9 \times \langle \left(\sqrt{4+5} \right)! \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0589 := \left(\sqrt{9} \right)!! - \langle (8+5) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0637 := 7 \times \langle (3+6) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$0648 := 8 \times \langle \left(\sqrt{4} + 6 \right) \parallel 0! \rangle$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 0659 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times 5! - \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 0709 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! - \langle 0! \parallel (7 \times 0)! \rangle \\
 0742 &:= \langle 2 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + (7 - 0)! \\
 0783 &:= 3!! - 8 + \langle 7 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 0791 &:= (\sqrt{1 \times 9})!! + \langle 7 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 0819 &:= 9 \times \langle (1 + 8) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 0847 &:= 7 \times \langle (4 + 8) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 0968 &:= 8 \times \langle (6 + (\sqrt{9})!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 0987 &:= 7 \times \langle (8 + (\sqrt{9})!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 \\
 1255 &:= 5 \times \langle 5^2 \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 1288 &:= 8 \times \langle (8 \times 2) \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 1342 &:= \langle 2 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times \langle 3! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 1359 &:= 9 \times \langle (5 \times 3) \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 1403 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \times (4! - 1) \\
 1438 &:= -8 + 3! \times \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 1449 &:= 9 \times \langle (4 \times 4) \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 1455 &:= 5 \times \langle (5 + 4!) \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 1494 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 9 \rangle \times (4 - 1)! \\
 1928 &:= 8 \times \langle (-2 + (\sqrt{9})!) \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 1944 &:= 4! \times \langle (4! / \sqrt{9}) \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 1952 &:= 2^5 \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 1984 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 8 \rangle \times (9 - 1) \\
 2809 &:= (\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle - 8)^2 \\
 3024 &:= 4! \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \times 3! \\
 3044 &:= 4 \times (\langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle + 3!!) \\
 3509 &:= -\langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle + 5 \times 3!! \\
 3955 &:= -5 + 5! \times \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 3 \rangle \\
 4356 &:= \langle (6! / 5!) \parallel 3! \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4392 &:= \langle (2 \times 9) \parallel 3 \rangle \times 4! \\
 4794 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + (\sqrt{\sqrt{74}})! \\
 4973 &:= -3 + 7! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 4 \rangle \\
 \\
 4974 &:= -\sqrt{4} + 7! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 4 \rangle \\
 4976 &:= 6! \times 7 - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 4 \rangle \\
 4979 &:= \sqrt{9} + 7! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 4 \rangle \\
 \\
 5904 &:= \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \times (\sqrt{9})!! / 5 \\
 00123 &:= \langle (3! \times 2) \parallel 1 \rangle + 0! + 0! \\
 \\
 00124 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (\langle (2 + 1)! \parallel 0! \rangle + 0!) \\
 00129 &:= 9 \times 2 + \langle \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00132 &:= \langle (2 \times 3! + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle + 0! \\
 00138 &:= (8 + \langle 3! \parallel 1 \rangle) \times (0! + 0!) \\
 00142 &:= 2 \times \langle ((4 - 1)! + 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00157 &:= 7 \times (5 - 1)! - \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00159 &:= \langle (\sqrt{9} \times 5) \parallel 10 \rangle - 0! \\
 00162 &:= 2 \times \langle (6 + 1 + 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00168 &:= (8 + 6) \times (\langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle + 0!) \\
 00179 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! / (-7 + \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle) - 0! \\
 00182 &:= \langle 2 \times (8 + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle + 0! \\
 00183 &:= 3 \times \langle (8 - 1 - 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00189 &:= 9 \times \langle (-8 + 10) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00192 &:= \langle 2 \times 9 + 1 \parallel 0! \rangle + 0! \\
 00193 &:= 3! \times (\langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 1 \rangle + 0!) + 0! \\
 00198 &:= (8 + 9 + 1) \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00213 &:= 3 \times \langle (1 + 2)! + 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00214 &:= \langle \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle \parallel 2 \rangle + 0! + 0! \\
 00215 &:= 5 - 1 + \langle \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00218 &:= 8 - 1 + \langle \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00219 &:= 9 - 1 + \langle \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00231 &:= \langle (1 \times 3 + 20) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00234 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (3 + 2) \rangle - \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00247 &:= 7 + \langle 4! \parallel (2 \times 0)! \rangle - 0! \\
 00248 &:= 8 \times \langle (\sqrt{4} + (2 \times 0)!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00249 &:= 9 + \langle 4! \parallel ((2 \times 0)! - 0!) \rangle \\
 00256 &:= 6 + \langle 5^2 \parallel 0! \rangle - 0! \\
 00261 &:= \langle (1 \times 6 + 20) \parallel 0! \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 00271 &:= \langle (1 \times 7 + 20) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00275 &:= 5 \times (7 - 2) \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00281 &:= \langle (1 \times 8 + 20) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00284 &:= 4 \times \langle (8 - (2 \times 0)!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00291 &:= \langle (1 \times 9 + 20) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00297 &:= \sqrt{7 + (\sqrt{9})!!} + 2 \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00312 &:= 2 \times 13! / \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle! \\
 00315 &:= 5 \times (1 + \langle 3! \parallel (0! + 0!) \rangle) \\
 00341 &:= (1 + 4! + 3!) \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00342 &:= 2 \times \langle (4! - 3! - 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00346 &:= 6! / \sqrt{4} - 3 - \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00349 &:= (9 - 4)! \times 3 - \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00369 &:= 9 \times \langle (6 - 3 + 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00372 &:= (\sqrt{2 + 7})! \times (\langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle + 0!) \\
 00374 &:= (4! + 7 + 3) \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00394 &:= -\sqrt{4} + (\sqrt{9})! \times 3! \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00395 &:= -5! + 9! / 3!! + \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00396 &:= 6 \times (9 - 3) \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00421 &:= -1 + 2 \times \langle \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00426 &:= 6 \times \langle (2 + 4 + 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00437 &:= 7 \times \langle 3! \parallel 4 \rangle - \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00452 &:= 2 \times (-5 + \langle (4! - 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 00453 &:= 3 \times (5! + \langle (\sqrt{4} + 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 00462 &:= 2 \times \langle (6 \times 4 - 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00463 &:= -3! + 6! - \langle (4! + 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00468 &:= \sqrt{8^6} - 4 \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00469 &:= -9 + 6! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle - 0! \\
 00473 &:= (-3! + \sqrt{7^4}) \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00476 &:= 6! + 7 - \langle (4! + 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00491 &:= (-1 + (\sqrt{9})!)! \times 4 + \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00495 &:= 5 \times 9 \times \langle (4 \times 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00498 &:= \langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (4 + 0! + 0!) \\
 00524 &:= 4!^2 - \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle - 0! \\
 00528 &:= 8 \times (-2 + 5)! \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00539 &:= (9 \times 3! - 5) \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 00542 &:= 2 \times \langle (-4! + \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00543 &:= 3 \times \langle (4! - 5 - 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00567 &:= 7 \times \langle \sqrt{65 - 0!} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00568 &:= 8 \times \langle (6 + (5 \times 0)!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00573 &:= 3!! - 7 \times \langle \sqrt{5 - 0!} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00579 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! - \langle (7 \times \sqrt{5 - 0!}) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00583 &:= (3! \times 8 + 5) \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00594 &:= (49 + 5) \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00627 &:= (-7 + 2^6) \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00634 &:= -4! + 3!! - \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle - 0! \\
 00639 &:= 9 \times \langle (3! + (6 \times 0)!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00653 &:= -\langle 3! \parallel 5 \rangle + 6! - 0! - 0! \\
 00654 &:= (\sqrt{4 + 5})!! - 6 \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00658 &:= (8 - 5)!! - \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle - 0! \\
 00684 &:= 4! + \sqrt{(8! - 6!) \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle} \\
 00689 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! - \langle (8 - 6 + 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00695 &:= -5 - 9 + 6! - \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00724 &:= (4 + 2)! - 7 + \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00731 &:= (13 - 7)! + \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00732 &:= 2 \times 3! \times \langle 7 - 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00743 &:= 3 \times \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle + 0! + 0! \\
 00781 &:= \sqrt{1^8 + 7!} \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00789 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + \langle (7 - 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00791 &:= -1 + 9! / 7! \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00792 &:= (2 + 9) \times \langle (7 \parallel 0!) + 0! \rangle \\
 00794 &:= \sqrt{4} + 9! / 7! \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00837 &:= 7! / 3! + 8 - \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00843 &:= 3 \times \langle (4 \times (8 - 0!)) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00846 &:= 6 \times \langle (\sqrt{4} \times (8 - 0!)) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00859 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! + 5! + 8 + \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00891 &:= 1 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00892 &:= (2 + 9) \times \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + 0! \\
 00917 &:= 7 \times \langle (-1 + (\sqrt{9})!)! + \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \rangle \\
 00946 &:= \langle \sqrt{64} \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 00956 &:= 6! - 5 + \langle (\sqrt{9} + 0!)! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00957 &:= 7!/5 - \langle ((\sqrt{9})! - 0!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00968 &:= (8 + 6!/9) \times \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 00984 &:= 4! \times \langle 8 - \sqrt{9} - 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01044 &:= 4 \times \langle (4! + 0! + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01045 &:= (5! - 4! - 0!) \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01048 &:= 8 \times \langle (4! - \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01055 &:= 5 \times \langle \langle \sqrt{5 - 0!} \parallel 1 \rangle \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01059 &:= 9 \times 5! - \langle (0! + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01069 &:= 9 \times (6 - 0!)! - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01089 &:= (98 + 0!) \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01155 &:= 5 \times \langle ((5 - 1)! - 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01197 &:= 7 \times \langle ((\sqrt{9})! + 11) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01205 &:= 5 \times \langle (0! + 2 + 1)! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01206 &:= 6 \times \langle (-0! + 21) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01224 &:= 4! \times \langle (2 + 2 + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01229 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! \times 2 - \langle 21 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01245 &:= 5 \times \langle 4! \parallel (-2 + \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle) \rangle \\
 01247 &:= 7!/4 - 2 - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01254 &:= (-4 + 5! - 2) \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01298 &:= \langle (8 - \sqrt{9})! - 2 \rangle \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01302 &:= \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \times \langle \langle 3! \parallel 1 \rangle + 0! \rangle \\
 01337 &:= 7 \times \langle (3 \times 3! + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01345 &:= -5! + 4! \times \langle 3! \parallel 1 \rangle + 0! \\
 01353 &:= (-3 + 5! + 3!) \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01364 &:= (4! + 6!) / 3! \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01369 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! + 6! - \langle (3! + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01375 &:= (5 + 7! \times 3) / \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01386 &:= 6 \times \langle (8 \times 3 - 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01397 &:= (7 + (\sqrt{9})!! / 3!) \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01399 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! + (\sqrt{9})!! - \langle (3 + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01407 &:= 7 \times \langle (-0! + \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01408 &:= (8 + (0! + 4)!) \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01429 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times 2)! \times \sqrt{4} - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01431 &:= (1 + 3!!) \times \sqrt{4} - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01437 &:= (-7 + 3!!) \times \sqrt{4} + \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01444 &:= \langle \langle 4 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle - 4 \rangle^{1+0!} \\
 01445 &:= (\sqrt{5 + 4})! \times \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle - 0! \\
 01447 &:= (7 - 4)! \times \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle + 0! \\
 01448 &:= 8 \times \langle (4! - (4 - 1)!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01451 &:= (1 + 5)! \times \sqrt{4} + \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01452 &:= (-2 + 5)! \times (\langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle + 0!) \\
 01463 &:= (3! + 6!) \times \sqrt{4} + \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01469 &:= \sqrt{9^6 \times 4} + \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01498 &:= -8 + (\sqrt{9})! \times \langle (4! + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01499 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times (9 + \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle) - 0! \\
 01506 &:= 6 \times \langle (0! + (5 - 1)!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01525 &:= 5^2 \times \langle (5 + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01547 &:= 7 \times \langle (4! - \sqrt{5 - 1}) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01549 &:= (9 + 4) \times 5! - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01559 &:= \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 5 \rangle \times (5 - 1)! - 0! \\
 01575 &:= 5 \times 7! / (5 + \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 01584 &:= 4! \times (8 - 5)! \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01595 &:= \langle 5 + 9 \parallel 5 \rangle \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01626 &:= 6 \times \langle (26 + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01669 &:= 9! / \sqrt{6^6} - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01672 &:= 2 \times 76 \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01688 &:= 8 \times \langle \langle (8 - 6) \parallel 1 \rangle \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01697 &:= 7! / \sqrt{9} + 6 + \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01746 &:= 6 \times \langle (4 \times 7 + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01749 &:= (-9 + 4! \times 7) \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01757 &:= 7 \times \left\langle \sqrt{\sqrt{5^{(7+1)}}} \parallel 0! \right\rangle \\
 01848 &:= \langle \langle (8 \times \sqrt{4}) \parallel 8 \rangle \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01879 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 7! / 8 - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01897 &:= 7 \times \langle \sqrt{9 \times 81} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01899 &:= 9 \times \langle (\sqrt{9} \times (8 - 1)) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01923 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 2 \rangle \times \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 1 \rangle + 0!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 01924 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 2 \rangle + (\sqrt{9})!! \times (1 + 0!) \\
 01933 &:= 3!^3 \times 9 - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01942 &:= -2 + 4! \times \langle (9 - 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01947 &:= (7 \times 4! + 9) \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 01955 &:= (5! - 5) \times \left((\sqrt{9})! + \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \\
 01967 &:= 7 \times \left\langle \sqrt{6! + 9} \parallel \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \right\rangle \\
 01968 &:= 8 \times 6 \times \left\langle (\sqrt{9} + 1) \parallel 0! \right\rangle \\
 02037 &:= 7 \times \langle \langle (3 \parallel 0!) - 2 \rangle \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02044 &:= -4 + \sqrt{4^{(0! \parallel (2 \times 0!))}} \\
 02099 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (\sqrt{9})!! - \langle (0! + 2)! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02149 &:= 9 \times \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle - 20 \\
 02184 &:= 4! \times \langle (8 + 1) \parallel (2 \times 0!) \rangle \\
 02196 &:= 6 \times (\sqrt{9})! \times \langle (1 + 2)! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02248 &:= 8 \times \langle (4! + 2 + 2) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02255 &:= 55 \times \langle (2 + 2) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02259 &:= 9 \times \langle 5^2 \parallel (2 \times 0!) \rangle \\
 02283 &:= (3! \times 8)^2 - \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02305 &:= \langle (5 \parallel 0!) - 3 \rangle^2 + 0! \\
 02346 &:= \left(\langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 3!! \right) \times (2 + 0!) \\
 02349 &:= 9 \times \langle (4 \times 3! + 2) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02352 &:= (-2 + 5! - 3!) \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02379 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! + 7!/3 - \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02394 &:= ((-4 + 9)! - 3!) \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02415 &:= (5! - 1 - 4) \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02419 &:= (9 + 1) \times \langle 4! \parallel 2 \rangle - 0! \\
 02436 &:= (6!/3! - 4) \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02439 &:= 9 \times \langle (3 + 4!) \parallel (2 \times 0!) \rangle \\
 02445 &:= 5 \times (\langle 4! \parallel 4 \rangle \times 2 + 0!) \\
 02454 &:= -4! + (5! - \sqrt{4}) \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02495 &:= 5 \times \left((\sqrt{9})!! - \langle (4! - 2) \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \\
 02499 &:= 9! / \left((\sqrt{9})! \times 4! \right) - \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02513 &:= -3! - 1 + 5! \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02514 &:= -(4 - 1)! + 5! \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02515 &:= -5 + 1 \times 5! \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02532 &:= 2 \times 3! + 5! \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02535 &:= 5 \times 3 + 5! \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02541 &:= (1^4 + 5!) \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02542 &:= \langle 2 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 5! \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02545 &:= \sqrt{5^4} + 5! \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02562 &:= (\sqrt{-2 + 6} + 5!) \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02568 &:= 8 \times 6 + 5! \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02583 &:= \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} + 5!} \right) \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02604 &:= (4 + (-0! + 6)!) \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02646 &:= \left\langle (6 \times \sqrt{4}) \parallel 6 \right\rangle \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02651 &:= \sqrt{1 + 5!} \times \langle (6 - 2)! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02667 &:= (7 + 6!/6) \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02684 &:= -4 + 8! / (-6 + \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 02859 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times 5!) \times 8 - \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02892 &:= 2 \times (\sqrt{9})! \times \langle (8/2)! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02904 &:= 4! \times \langle (0! + 9 + 2) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 02943 &:= \langle 3 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times 92 - 0! \\
 02964 &:= 4 \times ((-6 + 9)!! + \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 02968 &:= 8 \times \left(6 \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 2 \rangle - 0! \right) \\
 02995 &:= 5 \times \left((\sqrt{9})!! - \langle ((\sqrt{9})! \times 2) \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \\
 03124 &:= 4 \times ((2 + 1)!! + \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 03142 &:= -2 + 4! \times \langle 13 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03164 &:= 4 \times (6! + \langle (1 + 3!) \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 03195 &:= 5 \times 9 \times \langle (1 + 3!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03264 &:= \sqrt{4^6} \times \langle (2 + 3) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03294 &:= (4! + \sqrt{9}) \times 2 \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03295 &:= 5 \times \left(-\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 2 \rangle + 3!! + 0! \right) \\
 03315 &:= 51 \times \langle (3! \parallel 3!) - 0! \rangle \\
 03343 &:= 3!! + 43 \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03355 &:= 55 \times \langle 3! \parallel (3 \times 0!) \rangle \\
 03384 &:= 4! \times \langle (8 + 3!) \parallel (3 \times 0!) \rangle \\
 03386 &:= 6! + \langle 8 \parallel 3! \rangle \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03396 &:= 6 \times (9 \times \langle 3! \parallel 3 \rangle - 0!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 03445 &:= 5 \times ((4!/4)! - \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 03482 &:= 2 \times (8!/4! + \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 03503 &:= \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle \times (5! - 3! - 0!) \\
 03509 &:= - \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle + 5! \times 30 \\
 03552 &:= 2^5 \times \langle (5 + 3!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03559 &:= - (\sqrt{9})! + (5! - 5) \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03595 &:= -5^{\sqrt{9}} + 5! \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03624 &:= 4! \times \langle (2 \times 6 + 3) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03658 &:= (-8 + 5! + 6) \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03661 &:= (-1 + 6) \times 6! + \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03696 &:= 6! + 96 \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03843 &:= \langle 3! \parallel (4!/8) \rangle \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03864 &:= 4! \times \langle (6 \times 8/3) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03865 &:= 5 \times (6! - 8 + \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 03904 &:= 4^{\sqrt{09}} \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03905 &:= 5 \times \left((\sqrt{09})!! + \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \\
 03906 &:= \left((6 - 0!)! + (\sqrt{9})! \right) \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03945 &:= -5! + 4^{(\sqrt{9})!} - \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03949 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^4 \times \sqrt{9} + \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03953 &:= -3! + 5! \times \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 3 \rangle - 0! \\
 03954 &:= (\sqrt{4+5})! \times \left((\sqrt{9})!! - \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \\
 03961 &:= (-1 + 6)! \times \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 3 \rangle + 0! \\
 03963 &:= -3! + \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle^{3-0!} \\
 03964 &:= 4 \times (6! + \langle (9 \times 3) \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 03965 &:= (56 + 9) \times \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03966 &:= -6! + 6 \times \left((\sqrt{9})!! + \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \\
 03968 &:= (8 + 6! / (\sqrt{9})!) \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 03984 &:= 4! \times \langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (3 - 0!) \\
 03999 &:= \langle (9 + \sqrt{9}) \parallel 9 \rangle \times \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04059 &:= 9 \times \sqrt{5! + 0!} \times \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04069 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times 6! - \langle (0! + 4!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04079 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times (7 - 0!)! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 04159 &:= - (\sqrt{9})!! + (5! - 1) \times \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04163 &:= \langle (3 \times 6) \parallel 1 \rangle \times (4! - 0!) \\
 04179 &:= - (\sqrt{9})!! + 7! - \langle 14 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04236 &:= \langle 6 \parallel 3! \rangle^2 - (4 + 0!)! \\
 04239 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times 3!! - \langle (2 \times 4) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04299 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times (\sqrt{9} \times 2)! - \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04333 &:= 3^3! \times 3! - \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04337 &:= (7 - 3)^{3!} + \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04338 &:= (8 \times 3 - 3!) \times \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04353 &:= 3 \times (5 + 3! \times \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 04373 &:= 3!^7 / \langle 3! \parallel 4 \rangle - 0! \\
 04386 &:= 6 \times (8 + 3 \times \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 04389 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 3!!) + \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04393 &:= \langle 3! \times \sqrt{9} \parallel 3 \rangle \times 4! + 0! \\
 04422 &:= 22 \times \langle (4! - 4) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04437 &:= 7! - 3 \times \langle (4! - 4) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04439 &:= 9! / 3^4 - \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04455 &:= 55 \times \langle (4 + 4) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04471 &:= 17 \times \langle (4! \parallel 4!) - 0! \rangle \\
 04473 &:= (3 + 7! / 4!) \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04494 &:= \langle 4! - \sqrt{9} \parallel 4 \rangle \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04579 &:= \left((\sqrt{9+7})! - 5 \right) \times \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04584 &:= (-4 + 8)! \times \langle (-5 + 4!) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04586 &:= -6 + (-8 + 5!) \times \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04589 &:= -\sqrt{9} + (-8 + 5!) \times \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04592 &:= (-2^{\sqrt{9}} + 5!) \times \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04596 &:= 6 \times \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 5 + \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \\
 04599 &:= (99 + 5!) \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04623 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel 2 \rangle + 6)^{\sqrt{4}} - 0! \\
 04674 &:= \left((-\sqrt{4} + 7)! - 6 \right) \times \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04693 &:= 3! \times \left((\sqrt{9})!! + \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \right) + 0! \\
 04709 &:= -90 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04718 &:= -81 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 04727 &:= -72 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04733 &:= (-\langle 3! \parallel 3! \rangle + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 04736 &:= -63 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04754 &:= -45 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04757 &:= -7!/5! + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04763 &:= -36 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04767 &:= 7! - (6 + 7) \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04772 &:= -27 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04781 &:= -18 + 7! - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04807 &:= 7! + 08 - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04824 &:= 4! \times \langle (2 \times 8 + 4) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04827 &:= 7! + 28 - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04836 &:= 6 \times \left(3!! + \langle 8 \parallel (\sqrt{4} + 0!) \rangle \right) \\
 04837 &:= 7! + 38 - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04838 &:= \langle (8 + 3) \parallel 8 \rangle \times \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04867 &:= 7! + 68 - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04871 &:= -1 + 7! - 8 \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04873 &:= -3! + 7! - \langle 8 \times \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04874 &:= \sqrt{4} + 7! - 8 \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04877 &:= 7! + 78 - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04879 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! \times 7 - \langle (8 \times \sqrt{4}) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04887 &:= 7! + 8 - \langle (8 \times \sqrt{4}) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04889 &:= \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8! \right) / 8 - \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04909 &:= \left((\sqrt{9})! + 0! \right)! - \langle (9 + 4) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04917 &:= 7! - 1 \times \sqrt{9} \times \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04919 &:= \left((\sqrt{9})! + 1 \right)! - \langle \sqrt{9} \times 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04927 &:= 7! - \langle (2 + 9) \parallel 4 \rangle + 0! \\
 04929 &:= (9 - 2)! - \langle (9 + \sqrt{4}) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04935 &:= \left(-5 + 3!!/\sqrt{9} \right) \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04937 &:= 7! - \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle - 40 \\
 04961 &:= \left(1 + 6! / (\sqrt{9})! \right) \times \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04972 &:= -2 + 7! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel (\sqrt{4} + 0!) \rangle \\
 04987 &:= 7! - \langle (8 - \sqrt{9}) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle - 0!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 04995 &:= 5 \times 9 \times \langle (9 + \sqrt{4}) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 04999 &:= \left((\sqrt{9})! + 9/9 \right)! - \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05009 &:= -\langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0! \rangle + (0! + 5 + 0!)! \\
 05019 &:= \left((\sqrt{9})! + 1 \right)! - \langle \sqrt{-0! + 5} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05027 &:= 7! - 2 - \langle 0! \parallel (5 \times 0!) \rangle \\
 05029 &:= (9 - 2)! - \langle 0! \parallel (5 \times 0!) \rangle \\
 05041 &:= (1 + \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 5! + 0! \\
 05042 &:= 2 \times \left(\langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle \times 5! + 0! \right) \\
 05061 &:= (1 + 6)! + \langle \sqrt{-0! + 5} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05081 &:= (-1 + 8)! + \langle (-0! + 5) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05091 &:= (-1 + 9 - 0!)! + \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05092 &:= (-2 + 9)! + 0! + \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05147 &:= 7! - 4 + \langle \sqrt{1 + 5!} \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05191 &:= \left(1 + (\sqrt{9})! \right)! + \langle 15 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05197 &:= \left(7! + (\sqrt{9})! \right) + \langle 15 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05248 &:= \langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times 2^{5+0!} \\
 05291 &:= \left(1 + (\sqrt{9})! \right)! + \langle 25 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05297 &:= 7! + (\sqrt{9})! + \langle 25 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05329 &:= \langle 9 - 2 \parallel 3 \rangle^{\sqrt{5-0!}} \\
 05424 &:= 4! \times \left(\langle \langle 2 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \parallel 5 \rangle + 0! \right) \\
 05466 &:= 6 \times (6! + \langle (4! - 5) \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 05467 &:= 7 \times \left(6! + \langle (\sqrt{4 + 5})! \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \\
 05522 &:= 22 \times \langle (5 \times 5) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05544 &:= 4! \times \langle (4! - 5/5) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05589 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times (5! - \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 05709 &:= (9 - 0!)! / 7 - \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05784 &:= 4! \times \langle (8 / (7 - 5))! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05793 &:= \langle 3 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 7! + (5 + 0!)! \\
 05803 &:= (3!! - 0!) \times 8 + \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05819 &:= \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 1 \right) \times 8 + \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05843 &:= (3!! + 4) \times 8 + \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05867 &:= (7 + 6!) \times 8 + \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 05895 &:= 5 \times 9 \times \langle (8+5) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 05904 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (\sqrt{09})! \rangle \times (5-0!) \\
 05964 &:= 4 \times (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 05967 &:= (7+6) \times 9 \times \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 06239 &:= 9 \times 3!! - \langle (-2+6)! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 06344 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 4 \rangle \times (\sqrt{36} - 0!) \\
 06393 &:= 3!! + 93 \times \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 06419 &:= 9 \times (-1+4)!! - \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 06439 &:= 9 \times 3!! - \langle 4 \parallel (6 \times 0)! \rangle \\
 06495 &:= -5 + 9^4 - \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 06497 &:= \langle 7 \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} + 6! + 0! \\
 06539 &:= 9 \times 3!! + 5! - \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 06655 &:= 55 \times \langle (6+6) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 06744 &:= 4! \times \langle (4 \times 7) \parallel (6 \times 0)! \rangle \\
 06832 &:= ((2+3)! - 8) \times \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 06952 &:= -2 + (5! - (\sqrt{9})!) \times \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 06955 &:= -5 + 5! \times (-\sqrt{9} + \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 06993 &:= \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (-9 + (6-0)!) \\
 07299 &:= 9 \times ((\sqrt{9})!! + \langle (2+7) \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 07597 &:= (-7 - (\sqrt{9})! + 5!) \times \langle 7 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 07755 &:= 55 \times \langle (7+7) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 07839 &:= 9 \times (3!! + \langle (8+7) \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 07865 &:= (-5+6!) \times \langle (8-7) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 07952 &:= (-2+5! - (\sqrt{9})!) \times \langle 7 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 07995 &:= -(5! + \sqrt{9}) \times ((\sqrt{9})! - \langle 7 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 08019 &:= 9 \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \times \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 08343 &:= \langle 3! + 4 \parallel 3 \rangle \times \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 08424 &:= (4! + 2) \times 4 \times \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 08439 &:= (9! - 3) / \langle 4 \parallel \sqrt{8+0!} \rangle \\
 08444 &:= 4 \times (\langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle \times 8 - 0!) \\
 08694 &:= (\langle 4! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 6!) \times (8+0!) \\
 08844 &:= 44 \times \sqrt{8! + \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle} \\
 08855 &:= 55 \times \langle (8+8) \parallel 0! \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 08964 &:= 4 \times (6! \times \sqrt{9} + \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 08974 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (7+9! / \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 08991 &:= ((-1 + (\sqrt{9})!)! - 9) \times \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09159 &:= (9+5!) \times \langle 1 + (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09168 &:= 8 \times 6 \times \langle 19 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09282 &:= \langle (2+8) \parallel 2 \rangle \times \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09348 &:= -\langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times (3! - ((\sqrt{9})! - 0)!) \\
 09373 &:= \langle (3+7) \parallel 3 \rangle \times \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09456 &:= 6! + (5! - 4!) \times \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09464 &:= \langle (4+6) \parallel 4 \rangle \times \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09555 &:= \langle (5+5) \parallel 5 \rangle \times \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09646 &:= \langle (6+4) \parallel 6 \rangle \times \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09664 &:= \sqrt{4^6} \times \langle (6+9) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09737 &:= \langle (7+3) \parallel 7 \rangle \times \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09828 &:= \langle (8+2) \parallel 8 \rangle \times \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09834 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 3! \rangle + 8! / (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \\
 09919 &:= \langle (9+1) \parallel 9 \rangle \times \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09955 &:= 55 \times \langle (9+9) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09966 &:= 66 \times \langle ((\sqrt{9})! + 9) \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 09984 &:= 4! \times 8 \times (-9 + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle) \\
 09989 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!) - \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle \\
 10275 &:= 5 \times (7 + 2^{\langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle}) \\
 10582 &:= (2 + 8 \times 5!) \times \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 10584 &:= 4! + 8 \times 5! \times \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 10593 &:= (3!! + \sqrt{9^5}) \times \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 10635 &:= 5 \times 3 \times (6! - \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle) \\
 10789 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 + (7! - \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle) \\
 10919 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! - 1)! \times \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle - 1 \\
 10997 &:= (7 + 9! / \sqrt{9}) / \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 10998 &:= (8! + (\sqrt{9})!) \times \sqrt{9} / \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 11025 &:= (5 \times \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle)^{1+1} \\
 11568 &:= 8 \times 6 \times \langle (5-1)! \parallel 1 \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12144 &:= 4!! / \langle (4 \times 1 - 2) \parallel 1 \rangle! \\
 12384 &:= 4! \times \langle 8 \parallel 3! \rangle \times (2 + 1)! \\
 13176 &:= \sqrt{6^{7-1}} \times \langle 3! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 13255 &:= 55 \times \langle (-2 + 3!)! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 13448 &:= \langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} \times (3 - 1) \\
 14219 &:= \left(\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle - 2 \right) \times \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 14379 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (7! - 3! - \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle) \\
 14397 &:= 7! \times \sqrt{9} - 3 \times \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 14455 &:= -5 + 5! / \sqrt{4} \times \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 14616 &:= (6! - (\sqrt{16})!) \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 14647 &:= 7^4 \times 6 + \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 14679 &:= (-\sqrt{9} \times 7 + 6!) \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 14873 &:= 3 \times (7! - \langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle) - 1 \\
 14879 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 7! - \langle (8 - 4)! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 14931 &:= (1 \times 3!! - 9) \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 14942 &:= (-2 + 4^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 14992 &:= -2 + \left((\sqrt{9})!! - (\sqrt{9})! \right) \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 14994 &:= \left((\sqrt{4 \times 9})! - (\sqrt{9})! \right) \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 15079 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 7! - \langle (-0! + 5) \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 15096 &:= (6! - \langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times (5 - 1)! \\
 15144 &:= 4! + \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle \times (5 + 1)! \\
 15162 &:= (2 + 6!) \times \langle \sqrt{-1 + 5} \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 15273 &:= 3 \times (7! + \langle \sqrt{25} \parallel 1 \rangle) \\
 15436 &:= 63 \times \langle 4! \parallel 5 \rangle + 1 \\
 15477 &:= 77 \times \langle (4 \times 5) \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 15696 &:= \left(-\langle 6 \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 6! \right) \times (5 - 1)! \\
 15851 &:= (1 + 5!) \times \langle (8 + 5 \parallel 1) \rangle \\
 16104 &:= 4! \times \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle \times 61 \\
 16446 &:= \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 4^{6+1} \\
 16742 &:= \langle 2 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times 761 \\
 16743 &:= -\langle 3! \parallel 4 \rangle + 7^{6+1} \\
 17249 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! \times 4! - \langle \sqrt{2+7} \parallel 1 \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17324 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (-2 + 3!) \rangle \times 71 \\
 17346 &:= 6! \times 4! + \langle 3! \parallel (7 - 1) \rangle \\
 18244 &:= \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle^2 - 8! \times 1 \\
 18264 &:= 4! \times \left(6! + \langle \sqrt{2 \times 8} \parallel 1 \rangle \right) \\
 18544 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 4 \rangle \times (-5 + 81) \\
 19344 &:= (-4! \times 4 + 3!!) \times \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 19375 &:= 5^{7-3} \times \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 19592 &:= (2^9 + 5!) \times \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 19844 &:= \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times \left(\langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle - 1 \right) \\
 19924 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 2 \rangle + (\sqrt{9^9} - 1) \\
 19974 &:= 4 \times 7! - (\sqrt{9})! \times \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 1 \rangle \\
 20048 &:= 8! / \sqrt{4} - \langle \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 20147 &:= 7! \times 4 - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle - 2 \\
 20909 &:= \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 0! \right) \times \left(\langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0! \rangle - 2 \right) \\
 22319 &:= \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 1 \rangle \times 3!! - 2/2 \\
 22338 &:= (8! + \langle 3! \parallel 3! \rangle^2) / 2 \\
 23266 &:= 6^6 / 2 - \langle 3! \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 23409 &:= \langle (-9 + (04)!) \parallel 3 \rangle^2 \\
 23496 &:= \langle 6 \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times (-4 + 3!! / 2) \\
 23593 &:= \langle 3 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (-5 + 3!!) - 2 \\
 23874 &:= -4^7 + 8! - \langle 3! \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 23994 &:= \langle 4 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 9 \times \langle 3! \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 24334 &:= 4^{3!} \times 3! - \langle 4! \parallel 2 \rangle \\
 24649 &:= \left(\left(\langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle - 6! \right) / 4 \right)^2 \\
 24964 &:= (4 + \langle (6 + 9) \parallel 4 \rangle)^2 \\
 26896 &:= \langle \langle (6 + 9) \parallel 8 \rangle + 6 \rangle^2 \\
 27883 &:= -3! + \langle (8 + 8) \parallel 7 \rangle^2 \\
 27889 &:= \langle \langle \sqrt{9} \times 8 - 8 \rangle \parallel 7 \rangle^2 \\
 28644 &:= \langle 4 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times 682 \\
 28764 &:= (-\langle 4! \parallel 6 \rangle + 7!) \times (8 - 2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29405 &:= (5! + 0!) \times \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 2 \\
 29524 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 2 \rangle \times \left(5! + \sqrt{(\sqrt{9})! - 2} \right) \\
 29748 &:= \left(-\langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 7! \right) \times \sqrt{9} \times 2 \\
 29789 &:= \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel (8 - 7) \rangle^{\sqrt{9}} - 2 \\
 29793 &:= \langle 3 \parallel -(\sqrt{9})! + 7 \rangle^{\sqrt{9}} + 2 \\
 29808 &:= \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle \times \left(8 + (\sqrt{9})!! / 2 \right) \\
 29848 &:= \langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times \left(8 + (\sqrt{9})!! \right) / 2 \\
 29994 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + (\sqrt{9})! \times (9 - 2)! \\
 30172 &:= -2 + (7! - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 3! \\
 30174 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (7! - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 3 \\
 30282 &:= \langle \sqrt{2 \times 8} \parallel 2 \rangle \times (0! + 3!!) \\
 30378 &:= (-8 + 7! + \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 3! \\
 30473 &:= 3! \times 7! + \langle (4! - 0!) \parallel 3 \rangle \\
 30474 &:= \left(-\sqrt{4} + 7! + \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \times 3! \\
 30476 &:= 6 \times 7! + \langle (4! - 0!) \parallel 3! \rangle \\
 30478 &:= -8 + (7! + \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 3! \\
 30504 &:= \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \times ((5 - 0!)! + 3!!) \\
 30606 &:= ((6 + 0!)! + \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 3! \\
 30636 &:= (\langle 6 \parallel 3! \rangle + (6 + 0!)!) \times 3! \\
 30879 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times 7! - \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + 3!! \\
 30897 &:= -7! + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel \sqrt{8 + 0!} \rangle^3 \\
 31899 &:= \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (8 - 1)^3 \\
 32085 &:= 5 \times \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle^2 - 3!! \\
 32448 &:= \langle (8 + \sqrt{4}) \parallel 4 \rangle^2 \times 3 \\
 32452 &:= (2 + 5!) \times \langle (4! + 2) \parallel 3! \rangle \\
 33534 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 3 \rangle \times (5! + 3 \times 3!) \\
 33768 &:= 8 \times 67 \times \langle 3! \parallel 3 \rangle \\
 33924 &:= (\sqrt{4} + 2^9) \times \langle 3! \parallel 3! \rangle \\
 34398 &:= 8! + 9 \times \left(\langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle - 3!! \right) \\
 34484 &:= -4 + 8! - 4! \times \langle 4! \parallel 3 \rangle \\
 34486 &:= \left(6! + \langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \right) \times 43
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34593 &:= \left(\langle 3! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 5! \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - 3 \\
 34599 &:= \left(\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 5! \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 3 \\
 34704 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (0 \times 7)! \rangle \times 4! \times 3! \\
 35448 &:= 8! - 4! \times \langle (4 \times 5) \parallel 3 \rangle \\
 35777 &:= 7 \times (7! + \langle 7 \parallel (-5 + 3!) \rangle) \\
 35939 &:= \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 3 \rangle^{\sqrt{9}} + 5 - 3 \\
 36432 &:= 23 \times 4! \times \langle 6 \parallel 3! \rangle \\
 37044 &:= 4 \times \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel (0 \times 7)! \rangle^3 \\
 37297 &:= \langle 7 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle^2 \times 7 - 3! \\
 37453 &:= 3!! \times \langle 5 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 7 + 3! \\
 37536 &:= 6^3! - 5! \times \langle 7 \parallel 3! \rangle \\
 37596 &:= (6! + \sqrt{9}) \times \langle 5 \parallel \sqrt{7 - 3} \rangle \\
 38155 &:= -5 + \langle 5 \parallel \sqrt{1 + 8} \rangle \times 3!! \\
 38428 &:= 8! - \langle 2 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times \langle 8 \parallel 3! \rangle \\
 38634 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 3! \rangle - 6! + 8! - 3!! \\
 38966 &:= 6! \times 6 \times 9 + \langle 8 \parallel 3! \rangle \\
 39105 &:= 5 \times \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle \times (-9 + 3!!) \\
 39302 &:= -2 + \left(0! + \langle 3 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \right)^3 \\
 39304 &:= (\langle 4 \parallel 03 \rangle - 9)^3 \\
 39375 &:= 5^{7-3} \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 3 \rangle \\
 39468 &:= 8! - 6! - 4 \times \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 3 \rangle \\
 39498 &:= 8! - \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times 9 + 3! \\
 39509 &:= -\langle 9 \parallel 0! \rangle + (5 + \sqrt{9})! - 3!! \\
 39658 &:= 8! - 5 + \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle - 3!! \\
 39687 &:= 7! / 8 \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle - 3 \\
 39688 &:= -8 + 8! - 6! + \langle 9 \parallel 3! \rangle \\
 39786 &:= -6 + 8 \times \left(7! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 3! \rangle \right) \\
 39789 &:= -\sqrt{9} + 8 \times \left(7! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 3! \rangle \right) \\
 39792 &:= 2^{\sqrt{9}} \times \left(7! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 3! \rangle \right) \\
 39828 &:= 8! - 2 \times \langle (8 \times \sqrt{9}) \parallel 3! \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 39834 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 3 \rangle + 8! - 9^3 \\
 39844 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 4 \rangle + 8! - (9 - 3)! \\
 39848 &:= 8! + \langle 4! \parallel 8 \rangle - (9 - 3)! \\
 39854 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 5 \rangle + 8! + 9 - 3!! \\
 39879 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 7!/8) \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 3 \rangle \\
 39918 &:= 8! - \left(1 + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle\right) \times 3! \\
 39924 &:= (4 \times 2)! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times 3! \\
 39942 &:= (2 \times 4)! - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 3! \\
 39948 &:= 8! - 4 \times \langle 9 \parallel (9/3) \rangle \\
 40058 &:= 8! - (5! + \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 40078 &:= 8! - \langle (-7 + \langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle)! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 40108 &:= 8! - \langle \langle (0! + 1) \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 40158 &:= 8! - \langle 5 + \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 40184 &:= -4! + 8! - \langle \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 40185 &:= -5! + 8! + \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle + 4 \\
 40199 &:= 9!/9 - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 40208 &:= 8! - \langle \langle 0! \parallel (2 \times 0)! \rangle \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 40238 &:= 8! - \langle \langle 3! + 2 \rangle \parallel \sqrt{04} \rangle \\
 40258 &:= 8! - \langle \langle 5 - 2 \rangle! \parallel \sqrt{04} \rangle \\
 40268 &:= 8! - \langle \langle 6 - (2 \times 0)! \rangle \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 40353 &:= (3 + 5)! + \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle + \sqrt{4} \\
 40362 &:= (2 + 6)! + \langle \langle 3 + 0! \rangle \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 40364 &:= (\sqrt{4} + 6)! + \langle \langle 3 + 0! \rangle \parallel 4 \rangle \\
 40378 &:= 8! - 7 + \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle + 4 \\
 40381 &:= 1 \times 8! + \langle 3! \parallel (0 \times 4)! \rangle \\
 40384 &:= \sqrt{4} + 8! + \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{04} \rangle \\
 40394 &:= \left(4!/\sqrt{9}\right)! + \langle \langle 3! + 0! \rangle \parallel 4 \rangle \\
 40401 &:= \langle \langle 10 \times \sqrt{4} \rangle \parallel 0! \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 40479 &:= -9 + 7 \times \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 4! \\
 40524 &:= (4 \times 2)! + \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle \times 4 \\
 40548 &:= 8! + 4! + \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle \times 4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 40564 &:= (\sqrt{4} + 6)! + \langle \langle 5 - 0! \rangle! \parallel 4 \rangle \\
 40698 &:= 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \times \langle \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle + \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 40869 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + 6!) \times \langle \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle - 4! \rangle \\
 40926 &:= (6! - 2) \times \langle \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle - 4 \rangle \\
 40938 &:= 8! + 3!! - \langle \langle 9 + 0! \rangle \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 40978 &:= 8! + 7 \times \langle 9 \parallel 04 \rangle \\
 40983 &:= 3!! + 8! - \langle \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle + 4 \rangle \\
 40998 &:= 8! + (\sqrt{9})!! - \langle \langle \sqrt{9} + 0! \rangle \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 42384 &:= 4! \times \langle 8 \parallel 3! \rangle + (2 \times 4)! \\
 43533 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 3 \rangle \times (-5 + 3!! - 4!) \\
 43648 &:= (8 - 4! + 6!) \times \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 43856 &:= 6! \times 5 + 8! - \langle 3! \parallel 4 \rangle \\
 43913 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 1 \rangle \times (\sqrt{9})!! - 3 - 4 \\
 43919 &:= \langle \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle \times (\sqrt{9})!! + 3 - 4 \rangle \\
 44164 &:= \langle \langle 4! - 6 \rangle \parallel 1 \rangle \times \langle 4! \parallel 4 \rangle \\
 44394 &:= (-4 + (\sqrt{9})!!) \times \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + \sqrt{4} \\
 44398 &:= 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \times 3!! - \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 44469 &:= \sqrt{9^6} \times \langle 4! \parallel 4 \rangle / 4 \\
 44528 &:= (8^2 + 5!) \times \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 44616 &:= 6! \times \langle \langle 1 \times 6 \rangle \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle - 4! \\
 44633 &:= -3 + 3!! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle - 4 \\
 44634 &:= -4 + 3!! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle - \sqrt{4} \\
 44636 &:= 6! \times \langle 3! \parallel (6 - 4) \rangle - 4 \\
 44639 &:= \sqrt{9} + 3!! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle - 4 \\
 44642 &:= (2 + 4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + \sqrt{4} \\
 44644 &:= (4!/4)! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 4 \\
 44646 &:= \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times 6! + \sqrt{4} + 4 \\
 44662 &:= -2 + 6! \times \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 4! \\
 44764 &:= (\sqrt{4} + 6!) \times \langle \langle 7 - 4 \rangle! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 44918 &:= 8! + 19 \times \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44942 &:= -2 + \langle (4! - \sqrt{9}) \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 45308 &:= 8! + (0! + 3!)! - \langle 5 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 45696 &:= (6! - (\sqrt{9})!) \times \langle (6!/5!) \parallel 4 \rangle \\
 45699 &:= \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (6! + 5) + 4! \\
 46344 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle + 3!! \times 64 \\
 46384 &:= -\langle 4! \parallel 8 \rangle + 3!^6 - 4! \\
 46535 &:= -5 + \langle 3! \parallel 5 \rangle \times (6! - 4) \\
 46605 &:= -\langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle + \sqrt{6^{(6 \times \sqrt{4})}} \\
 46619 &:= -\langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 1 \rangle + 6^6 + 4! \\
 46693 &:= \langle 3 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 6^6 + 4 \\
 46944 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle + (\sqrt{9})!^6 + 4! \\
 46968 &:= (-8 + 6!) \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 6 \rangle - 4! \\
 46978 &:= 8! \times 7 / (\sqrt{9})! - \langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 47089 &:= \left(\langle \sqrt{9} \parallel (8 \times 0)! \rangle \times 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 47334 &:= (\langle 4! \parallel 3! \rangle + 3!!) \times \sqrt{7^4} \\
 47424 &:= 4 \times 2 \times \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \times 4! \\
 47448 &:= 8 \times 4! \times \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle + 4! \\
 47524 &:= (\langle (4! - 2) \parallel 5 \rangle - 7)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 49005 &:= 5 \times (\langle 0! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 9)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 49236 &:= \langle 6 \parallel 3! \rangle \times (2 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 4!) \\
 49675 &:= -5 + 7! + 6! \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \\
 49923 &:= 3 \times \langle (2 \times (\sqrt{9})!) \parallel 9 \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 50765 &:= (-5 + 6!) \times \langle 7 \parallel (0 \times 5)! \rangle \\
 50907 &:= \langle 7 \parallel 0! \rangle \times (-\sqrt{9} + (0! + 5)!) \\
 51479 &:= 9!/7 - \langle 4! \parallel 1 \rangle - 5! \\
 53694 &:= (\langle 4! \parallel 9 \rangle - 6!) \times (3! - 5!) \\
 54336 &:= 6^3! + \langle 3! \parallel 4 \rangle \times 5! \\
 57148 &:= 8! + \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 1 \rangle + 7^5 \\
 58444 &:= \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle^{\sqrt{-4+8}} - 5! \\
 59014 &:= -4! - \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle + 9^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 59018 &:= -\langle \sqrt{8+1} \parallel 0! \rangle + 9^5 \\
 59024 &:= -4 - \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle + 9^5 \\
 59028 &:= -\langle \sqrt{8/2} \parallel 0! \rangle + 9^5 \\
 59109 &:= \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle - 1 + 9^5 \\
 59134 &:= 4! + \langle 3! \parallel 1 \rangle + 9^5 \\
 59291 &:= \langle (1 + \sqrt{9})! \parallel 2 \rangle + 9^5 \\
 59294 &:= \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 2 + 9^5 \\
 59345 &:= \langle (5 + 4!) \parallel 3! \rangle + 9^5 \\
 59433 &:= 3! \times \langle 3! \parallel 4 \rangle + 9^5 \\
 59497 &:= 7 \times \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 4 \rangle + 9^5 \\
 59938 &:= 8! + 3^9 - \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 5 \rangle \\
 60439 &:= 9!/3! - \langle 4 \parallel (0 \times 6)! \rangle \\
 62436 &:= (6! + 3!) \times \langle 4 \times 2 \parallel 6 \rangle \\
 62494 &:= \left(\langle 4! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle + 4 \right)^2 - 6 \\
 62638 &:= \langle 8 \parallel 3! \rangle \times 6! - 2 + 6! \\
 63888 &:= \langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{8 \times 8} \rangle \times (3! + 6!) \\
 64728 &:= \langle \sqrt{8^2} \parallel 7 \rangle \times (4! + 6!) \\
 64944 &:= 4! \times (\sqrt{4} + 9) \times \langle 4! \parallel 6 \rangle \\
 64984 &:= 4^8 - \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \times 6 \\
 66898 &:= \langle 8 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times (86 + 6!) \\
 66954 &:= \langle 4 + 5 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle \times 6! - 6 \\
 66996 &:= 6! \times \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 6 \times 6 \\
 68395 &:= -5 + \langle 9 \parallel (-3 + 8) \rangle \times 6! \\
 69399 &:= -9 + \langle 9 \parallel 3! \rangle \times (\sqrt{9} + 6!) \\
 69549 &:= \left(\langle 9 \parallel (\sqrt{4}) + 5 \rangle \right) \times (-\sqrt{9} + 6!) \\
 70682 &:= 2 \times (8! + \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle - 7!) \\
 71065 &:= 5^6 + \langle 0! \parallel 1 \rangle \times 7! \\
 71999 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! \times \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle - 1 + 7! \\
 73444 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 4 \rangle \times 43 \times 7 \\
 74347 &:= 7 \times 43 \times \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \\
 77448 &:= 8! + (\langle 4! \parallel 4! \rangle + 7!) \times 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 79989 &:= 9! - \left(8! + \langle 9 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle\right) \times 7 \\
 80472 &:= \left(2 \times 7! - \langle \sqrt{4} \parallel 0! \rangle\right) \times 8 \\
 80529 &:= -9 + 2 \times (-\langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!) \\
 80532 &:= 2 \times (-3 - \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!) \\
 80538 &:= (-8 + 3!) \times (\langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle - 8!) \\
 80583 &:= -3! + 8! - \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8! \\
 80589 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 8! - \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle - 8! \\
 80598 &:= 8! + 9 - \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8! \\
 80662 &:= 2 \times (\langle (6/6) \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!) \\
 80682 &:= 2 \times (\langle (8-6) \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!) \\
 80698 &:= 8! - \sqrt{9} + \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8! \\
 80728 &:= 8! \times 2 + \langle (7+0!) \parallel 8 \rangle \\
 80742 &:= 2 \times \langle (-\sqrt{4} + 7) \parallel 0! \rangle + 8! \\
 80762 &:= 2 \times (\langle 6 \parallel (7 \times 0!) \rangle + 8!) \\
 80782 &:= 2 \times (8! + \langle 7 \parallel (0 \times 8!) \rangle) \\
 80794 &:= \sqrt{4} \times \left(\langle \sqrt{9} \rangle! + \langle 7 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!\right) \\
 80804 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (0! + \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!) \\
 80842 &:= 2 \times \left(\langle (\sqrt{4} + 8) \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!\right) \\
 80883 &:= 3 \times (8! + \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle) - 8!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 80942 &:= 2 \times (\langle (4! - 9) \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!) \\
 80982 &:= 2 \times (\langle (8+9) \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!) \\
 85344 &:= \left(\langle 4 \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle + 3!!\right) \times (5! - 8) \\
 87744 &:= (4! \times \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle + 7!) \times 8 \\
 90567 &:= (7! \times 6 - \langle 5 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 92364 &:= (-4 + 6!) \times \langle (3! \times 2) \parallel 9 \rangle \\
 92493 &:= (3!! - \sqrt{9}) \times \langle (4!/2) \parallel 9 \rangle \\
 93024 &:= \left(-\sqrt{4} + \langle 2 \parallel 0! \rangle\right)! / (3! + 9!) \\
 93504 &:= \left(-\langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle + 5^{3!}\right) \times (\sqrt{9})! \\
 93955 &:= -5 + 5! \times \left(\langle \sqrt{9} \rangle!! + \langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle\right) \\
 94058 &:= \langle (8+5) \parallel 0! \rangle \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + (\sqrt{9})!!\right) \\
 94794 &:= (4 \times \sqrt{9})! / 7! - \langle 4! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \\
 96624 &:= (4! + 2 \times 6!) \times \langle 6 \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \\
 98404 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle^{\sqrt{4}} + 8! + \sqrt{9} \\
 99645 &:= 5 \times \left(\langle 4! \parallel 6 \rangle + \sqrt{9^9}\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

3 Number Patterns

In 1966, Madachy [21] pp. 174-175, gave an idea of number patterns writing as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 3^4 \times 425 &:= 34425 \\
 3^4 \times 4250 &:= 344250 \\
 3^4 \times 42500 &:= 3442500
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 31^2 \times 325 &:= 312325 \\
 31^2 \times 3250 &:= 3123250 \\
 31^2 \times 32500 &:= 31232500
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 73 \times 9 \times 42 &:= 73942 \\
 73 \times 9 \times 420 &:= 739420 \\
 73 \times 9 \times 4200 &:= 7394200
 \end{aligned}$$

Based on same idea as above, there are some concatenation-type selfie numbers, those can be extended in patterned form just multiplying successively by 10. See below examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 305 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 5 \\
 3050 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 50 \\
 30500 &:= \langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 500 \\
 \\
 396 &:= \langle 3! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times 6 \\
 3960 &:= \langle 3! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times 60 \\
 39600 &:= \langle 3! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times 600 \\
 \\
 492 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times 2 \\
 4920 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times 20 \\
 49200 &:= \langle 4! \parallel (\sqrt{9})! \rangle \times 200 \\
 \\
 1446 &:= \left(-1 + \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \right) \times 6 \\
 14460 &:= \left(-1 + \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \right) \times 60 \\
 144600 &:= \left(-1 + \langle 4! \parallel \sqrt{4} \rangle \right) \times 600 \\
 \\
 1476 &:= (-1 + \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle) \times 6 \\
 14760 &:= (-1 + \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle) \times 60 \\
 147600 &:= (-1 + \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle) \times 600 \\
 \\
 1968 &:= \langle (1 + \sqrt{9})! \parallel 6 \rangle \times 8 \\
 19680 &:= \langle (1 + \sqrt{9})! \parallel 6 \rangle \times 80 \\
 196800 &:= \langle (1 + \sqrt{9})! \parallel 6 \rangle \times 800 \\
 \\
 3905 &:= \left(3!! + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \times 5 \\
 39050 &:= \left(3!! + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \times 50 \\
 390500 &:= \left(3!! + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \times 500 \\
 \\
 10285 &:= \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle^2 \times 85 \\
 102850 &:= \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle^2 \times 850 \\
 1028500 &:= \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle^2 \times 8500 \\
 \\
 10635 &:= (-\langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle + 6!) \times 3 \times 5 \\
 106350 &:= (-\langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle + 6!) \times 3 \times 50 \\
 1063500 &:= (-\langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle + 6!) \times 3 \times 500 \\
 \\
 10648 &:= \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle^{6/\sqrt{4}} \times 8 \\
 106480 &:= \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle^{6/\sqrt{4}} \times 80 \\
 1064800 &:= \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle^{6/\sqrt{4}} \times 800 \\
 \\
 14056 &:= \langle (1 + 4!) \parallel 0! \rangle \times 56 \\
 140560 &:= \langle (1 + 4!) \parallel 0! \rangle \times 560 \\
 1405600 &:= \langle (1 + 4!) \parallel 0! \rangle \times 5600 \\
 \\
 15129 &:= \langle (-1 + 5) \parallel 1 \rangle^2 \times 9 \\
 151290 &:= \langle (-1 + 5) \parallel 1 \rangle^2 \times 90 \\
 1512900 &:= \langle (-1 + 5) \parallel 1 \rangle^2 \times 900 \\
 \\
 19225 &:= \left(1 + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 2 \rangle^2 \right) \times 5 \\
 192250 &:= \left(1 + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 2 \rangle^2 \right) \times 50 \\
 1922500 &:= \left(1 + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 2 \rangle^2 \right) \times 500 \\
 \\
 25405 &:= ((2 + 5)! + \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 5 \\
 254050 &:= ((2 + 5)! + \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 50 \\
 2540500 &:= ((2 + 5)! + \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 500 \\
 \\
 25575 &:= (\langle (2 + 5) \parallel 5 \rangle + 7!) \times 5 \\
 255750 &:= (\langle (2 + 5) \parallel 5 \rangle + 7!) \times 50 \\
 2557500 &:= (\langle (2 + 5) \parallel 5 \rangle + 7!) \times 500 \\
 \\
 30576 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle - 5 + 7!) \times 6 \\
 305760 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle - 5 + 7!) \times 60 \\
 3057600 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle - 5 + 7!) \times 600
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 30606 &:= ((3! + 0!)! + \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 6 \\ 306060 &:= ((3! + 0!)! + \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 60 \\ 3060600 &:= ((3! + 0!)! + \langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 30636 &:= ((3! + 0!)! + \langle 6 \parallel 3! \rangle) \times 6 \\ 306360 &:= ((3! + 0!)! + \langle 6 \parallel 3! \rangle) \times 60 \\ 3063600 &:= ((3! + 0!)! + \langle 6 \parallel 3! \rangle) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 30667 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle + 6! \times 6) \times 7 \\ 306670 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle + 6! \times 6) \times 70 \\ 3066700 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel 0! \rangle + 6! \times 6) \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33044 &:= (3!! + \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 44 \\ 330440 &:= (3!! + \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 440 \\ 3304400 &:= (3!! + \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 4400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33124 &:= \langle (3 \times 3) \parallel 1 \rangle^2 \times 4 \\ 331240 &:= \langle (3 \times 3) \parallel 1 \rangle^2 \times 40 \\ 3312400 &:= \langle (3 \times 3) \parallel 1 \rangle^2 \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33327 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel 3 \rangle + 3!)^2 \times 7 \\ 333270 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel 3 \rangle + 3!)^2 \times 70 \\ 3332700 &:= (\langle 3! \parallel 3 \rangle + 3!)^2 \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39052 &:= (3!! + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 52 \\ 390520 &:= (3!! + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 520 \\ 3905200 &:= (3!! + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 5200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39105 &:= (3!! - 9) \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \times 5 \\ 391050 &:= (3!! - 9) \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \times 50 \\ 3910500 &:= (3!! - 9) \times \langle 1 \parallel 0! \rangle \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39768 &:= (-\langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 7! - 6) \times 8 \\ 397680 &:= (-\langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 7! - 6) \times 80 \\ 3976800 &:= (-\langle 3! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 7! - 6) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40959 &:= \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \times (-9 + 5!) \times 9 \\ 409590 &:= \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \times (-9 + 5!) \times 90 \\ 4095900 &:= \langle 4 \parallel 0! \rangle \times (-9 + 5!) \times 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45909 &:= (\langle (\sqrt{4} + 5) \rangle! + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 9 \\ 459090 &:= (\langle (\sqrt{4} + 5) \rangle! + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 90 \\ 4590900 &:= (\langle (\sqrt{4} + 5) \rangle! + \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 47424 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \times 4! \times 2 \times 4 \\ 474240 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \times 4! \times 2 \times 40 \\ 4742400 &:= \langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \times 4! \times 2 \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 47488 &:= (\langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \times 4! + 8) \times 8 \\ 474880 &:= (\langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \times 4! + 8) \times 80 \\ 4748800 &:= (\langle 4! \parallel 7 \rangle \times 4! + 8) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 49923 &:= \langle (4 \times \sqrt{9}) \parallel 9 \rangle^2 \times 3 \\ 499230 &:= \langle (4 \times \sqrt{9}) \parallel 9 \rangle^2 \times 30 \\ 4992300 &:= \langle (4 \times \sqrt{9}) \parallel 9 \rangle^2 \times 300 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 60846 &:= (\langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!/4) \times 6 \\ 608460 &:= (\langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!/4) \times 60 \\ 6084600 &:= (\langle 6 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!/4) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63084 &:= (6! + \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 84 \\ 630840 &:= (6! + \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 840 \\ 6308400 &:= (6! + \langle 3 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 8400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 68085 &:= (6! + \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 85 \\ 680850 &:= (6! + \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 850 \\ 6808500 &:= (6! + \langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle) \times 8500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 80802 &:= (\langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!) \times 02 \\ 80802 &:= (\langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!) \times 020 \\ 80802 &:= (\langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + 8!) \times 0200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69092 &:= \left(6! + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \times 92 \\ 690920 &:= \left(6! + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \times 920 \\ 6909200 &:= \left(6! + \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0! \rangle \right) \times 9200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 80832 &:= (8! + \langle (0! + 8) \parallel 3! \rangle) \times 2 \\ 808320 &:= (8! + \langle (0! + 8) \parallel 3! \rangle) \times 20 \\ 8083200 &:= (8! + \langle (0! + 8) \parallel 3! \rangle) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69408 &:= 6 \times (\sqrt{9})! \times \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 8 \\ 694080 &:= 6 \times (\sqrt{9})! \times \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 80 \\ 6940800 &:= 6 \times (\sqrt{9})! \times \langle 4! \parallel 0! \rangle \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 90782 &:= \left(\langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0! \rangle + 7! + 8! \right) \times 2 \\ 907820 &:= \left(\langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0! \rangle + 7! + 8! \right) \times 20 \\ 9078200 &:= \left(\langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 0! \rangle + 7! + 8! \right) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69435 &:= \left(\langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 4!^3 \right) \times 5 \\ 694350 &:= \left(\langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 4!^3 \right) \times 50 \\ 6943500 &:= \left(\langle 6 \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle + 4!^3 \right) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 91295 &:= \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 1 \rangle^2 \times 95 \\ 912950 &:= \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 1 \rangle^2 \times 950 \\ 9129500 &:= \langle \sqrt{9} \parallel 1 \rangle^2 \times 9500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 80482 &:= \left(-\langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + \sqrt{4} + 8! \right) \times 2 \\ 804820 &:= \left(-\langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + \sqrt{4} + 8! \right) \times 20 \\ 8048200 &:= \left(-\langle 8 \parallel 0! \rangle + \sqrt{4} + 8! \right) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 99225 &:= \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle^2 \times 25 \\ 992250 &:= \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle^2 \times 250 \\ 9922500 &:= \langle (\sqrt{9})! \parallel \sqrt{9} \rangle^2 \times 2500 \end{aligned}$$

4 Summary: Selfie Numbers

The author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides of the expressions are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Subsections below give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, etc. In two variables, we obtained selfie numbers with **binomial coefficients**, **S-gonal numbers**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc. The other way of writing selfie numbers is by use of permutable powers, where bases and exponents are of same digits. See the subsection below with some examples.

4.1 Permutable Powers

Below are some examples of **permutable power selfie numbers**. By **permutable powers**, we understand that bases and exponents are of same digits with different permutations. Some times we may call them as **flexible power selfie numbers**.

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{1} := 1^1 & \mathbf{3529} := -3^3 + 5^5 + 2^9 - 9^2 \\
 \mathbf{23} := -2^2 + 3^3 & \mathbf{4316} := 4^6 + 3^1 + 1^4 + 6^3 \\
 \mathbf{1239} := 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 & \mathbf{4355} := 4^5 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 5^5 \\
 \mathbf{1364} := 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3 & \mathbf{39339} := -3^3 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 9^3 \\
 \mathbf{1654} := -1^6 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 4^5 & \mathbf{46350} := -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 0^4 \\
 \mathbf{1837} := 1^8 - 8^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 & \mathbf{46360} := 4^0 + 6^6 - 3^4 - 6^3 + 0^6 \\
 \mathbf{2137} := -2^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 7^2 & \mathbf{397612} := 3^2 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 6^7 + 1^9 + 2^3 \\
 \mathbf{2173} := -2^3 + 1^2 - 7^1 + 3^7 & \mathbf{423858} := 4^3 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 5^8 + 8^5 \\
 \mathbf{2537} := 2^5 - 5^2 + 3^7 + 7^3 & \mathbf{637395} := 6^5 + 3^3 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 9^6 + 5^7 \\
 \mathbf{3125} := -3^2 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 5^5 & \mathbf{758014} := 7^7 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 0^5 + 1^4 - 4^8 \\
 \mathbf{3275} := -3^3 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 5^5 & \mathbf{778530} := 7^7 + 7^3 + 8^5 - 5^7 + 3^0 + 0^8 \\
 \mathbf{3435} := 3^3 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 5^5 & \mathbf{804637} := 8^0 + 0^4 - 4^8 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 7^7
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \mathbf{15647982} := 1^5 - 5^9 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 7^7 - 9^1 + 8^8 + 2^6 \\
 \mathbf{17946238} := 1^6 + 7^8 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 6^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 8^7 \\
 \mathbf{57396108} := -5^6 + 7^9 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^7 + 1^1 + 0^0 + 8^8 \\
 \mathbf{134287690} := 1^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 8^9 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 0^1 \\
 \mathbf{387945261} := 3^3 + 8^2 + 7^6 + 9^9 + 4^7 + 5^8 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 1^5 \\
 \mathbf{392876054} := 3^0 + 9^9 - 2^2 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 + 0^3 - 5^4 + 4^6 \\
 \mathbf{392876540} := -3^0 + 9^9 - 2^4 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 - 5^3 + 4^6 + 0^2
 \end{array}$$

More details can be seen in author's work [34].

4.2 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples in both orders:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{13825} := 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5} & = ((5 - 2) \times 8)^3 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{14641} := (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 & = (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{15552} := (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2 & = 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{16377} := (1 + 6 - 3)^7 - 7 & = -7 + (7 - 3)^{6+1} \\
 \mathbf{23328} := (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 & = (8 - 2)^{3+3} / 2 \\
 \mathbf{116565} := (-1 + 16) \times (-5 + 6^5) & = 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1) \\
 \mathbf{131072} := (1 + 3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 & = 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 147419 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 = 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\
 147429 &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 = 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\
 147491 &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 = 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\
 156252 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 = 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6 - 5} + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits:

$$\begin{aligned}
 656250 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 0 = 0 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656251 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 1 = 1 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656252 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 2 = 2 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656253 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 3 = 3 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656254 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 4 = 4 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656255 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 5 = 5 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656256 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 6 = 6 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656257 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 7 = 7 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656258 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 8 = 8 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656259 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 9 = 9 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [26, 27].

4.3 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\
 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! \\
 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! \\
 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\
 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\
 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\
 80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & 403199 &:= 40319 + 9! \\
 317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! & 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\
 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! & 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\
 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! & 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\
 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!
 \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and are only with positive and negative coefficients. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways:

$$\begin{aligned}
 35280 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35281 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 35282 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35283 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35284 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35285 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35286 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35287 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35288 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35289 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [39, 40].

4.4 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples in both orders, i.e., in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$1764 := 1 \times (7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$
$2378 := -23 + \sqrt{7^8}$	$1024 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 1}$
$19454 := 19 \times 4^5 - \sqrt{4}$	$1296 := 6^{\sqrt{9+2-1}}$
$19459 := 19 \times 4^5 + \sqrt{9}$	$2189 := \sqrt{9^{8-1}} + 2$
$19684 := 1 + \sqrt{9\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}/4}}$	$3867 := (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 3$
$331779 := 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} = \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3$	$9375 := \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 9}$
$839793 := (-8 + (-3 + 9)^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 3$	$12289 := \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2 \times 2} + 1$
$839795 := -8 + (-3 + 9)^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 5$	$19693 := 3^9 + 6 + \sqrt{9} + 1$
$839804 := (-8 + (3 - 9)^8 + 0) / \sqrt{4}$	$42436 := (6 \times 34 + 2)^{\sqrt{4}}$
$839816 := (8 + (3 - 9)^8) / \sqrt{\sqrt{16}}$	$59051 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} + 0 + 9^5$
$995544 := ((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 54) \times 4$	$999901 := (10^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - 99$
$999916 := -9 \times 9 - \sqrt{9} + (9 + 1)^6$	$999991 := (1^9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9$
$999976 := -\sqrt{9} \times 9 + \sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9} + 7)^6$	

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details refer author's work [26, 27].

4.5 Factorial and Square-Root

Below are some examples with **factorial** and **square-root** written in both ways, i.e., in **digit's order** and its reverse

$$\begin{aligned}
 936 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! &= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 1296 &:= \sqrt{(1+2)!^9 / 6} &= 6^{(\sqrt{9+2-1})}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2896 &:= 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) = (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\ 342995 &:= (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 = -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\ 759375 &:= (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 = (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7}. \\ 759381 &:= 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 = -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5040 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 0 = 0 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\ 5041 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 1 = 1 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\ 5042 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 2 = 2 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\ 5043 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 = 3 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\ 5044 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 4 = 4 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\ 5045 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 5 = 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\ 5046 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 6 = 6 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\ 5047 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 7 = 7 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\ 5048 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 8 = 8 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\ 5049 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 9 = 9 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \end{aligned}$$

The following examples are in **digit's order** and its **reverse** separately:

$120 := ((1 + 2)! - 0)!;$	$25 := 5^2$
$127 := -1 + 2^7$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$
$1673 := -1 - 6 + 7!/3$	$289 := (9 + 8)^2$
$1679 := 1 + (-6 + 7!)/\sqrt{9}$	$3894 := (\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(\sqrt{9})!^8}) \times 3$
$1680 := (1 + 6)!/\sqrt{8 + 0!}$	$4957 := 7! - 59 - 4!$
$38970 := -3!! + 8! - 9 \times 70$	$6992 := 2^9 + 9 \times 6!$
$38986 := -3 + 8! - \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 8)^6}$	$26493 := (2 + 6)! - 4!^{\sqrt{9}} - 3$
$40310 := (\sqrt{4^{03}})! - 10$	$30792 := 3! \times ((0 + 7)! + 92)$
$90894 := -(\sqrt{9})! + ((0! + 8)! + (\sqrt{9})!!)/4$	$54476 := (5! + 4!^4 - 7!)/6$
$91560 := ((\sqrt{9})! + 1)! + 5! \times (6! + 0!)$	$75989 := \sqrt{9} \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!!) + 5^7$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer author's work [26, 27, 28].

4.6 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n + 1) = F(n) + F(n - 1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Below are examples of **selfie numbers** by use of **Fibonacci sequence values**. This we have done in different situations, such as using $F(\cdot)$ and $F(F(\cdot))$ in separate works. See below examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 143 &:= -1 + F(4 \times 3) &= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\
 986 &:= F(9) \times (F(8) + F(6)) &= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\
 1178 &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) &= F(8) + F(7) \times F(11) \\
 2585 &:= F(2) + F(5 + 8 + 5) &= F(5 + 8 + 5) + F(2) \\
 12819 &:= 1 + F(2 \times (8 - 1)) \times F(9) &= F(9) \times F((-1 + 8) \times 2) + 1 \\
 24297 &:= F(2 \times 4) \times F(2 + 9) \times F(7) &= F(7) \times F(9 + 2) \times F(4 \times 2) \\
 39394 &:= -3 + 93 + F(9)^{F(4)} &= (-4 + F(9)) \times 3 + F(9)^3 \\
 74997 &:= -7 \times 4 + F(9 + 9 + 7) &= F(7 + 9 + 9) - 4 \times 7 \\
 87937 &:= -8 + F(7) \times F(9 \times 3 - 7) &= F(7) \times F(3 \times 9 - 7) - 8 \\
 98703 &:= 9 \times (F(8) + F(7 \times 03)) &= (F(3 \times 07) + F(8)) \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34 &:= F(3 \times F(4)) & 36 &:= 6^{F(3)} \\
 233 &:= F(F(-2 + 3 \times 3)) & 143 &:= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\
 630 &:= F(F(6)) \times 30 & 231 &:= F(13) - 2 \\
 1178 &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) & 377 &:= F(-7 + 7 \times 3) \\
 2079 &:= (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 9 & 986 &:= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\
 4864 &:= F(F(4))^8 \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(4))) & 1165 &:= 5 \times F(F(6 \times 1 + 1)) \\
 8759 &:= -F(9 - 5)^7 + F(F(8)) & 1596 &:= F(F(6) + 9) - F(F(F(5 - 1))) \\
 8849 &:= -9 \times F(F(F(F(F(4)))) - 8) + F(F(8)) & 2592 &:= F(2 \times 9) + F(5 + F(2)) \\
 9349 &:= -F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + F(F(F(-3 + 9))) & 9756 &:= F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 7 \times F(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 834660 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 0 = 0 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834661 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 1 = 1 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834662 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 2 = 2 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834663 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 3 = 3 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834664 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 4 = 4 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834665 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 5 = 5 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834666 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 6 = 6 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834667 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 7 = 7 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834668 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 8 = 8 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834669 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 9 = 9 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21960 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21961 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21962 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21963 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21964 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21965 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21966 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21967 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21968 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21969 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2.
 \end{aligned}$$

First three blocks are in both ways. In the last block the first column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [36, 37].

4.7 Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

The examples given in above subsections are with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence** numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1069 &:= T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9)) & 874 &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8) \\
 1081 &:= T(1 + T(08 + 1)) & 0105 &:= 50 + T(10) \\
 2887 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7) & 1155 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1) \\
 4965 &:= T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5))) & 1224 &:= T(T(T(4) - T(T(2)))) - 2 + 1 \\
 4999 &:= 49 + T(99) & 2418 &:= T(81) - T(42) \\
 99545 &:= T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5 & 99632 &:= 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9) \\
 99546 &:= T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6. & 99633 &:= 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9).
 \end{aligned}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 2210 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 0 = 0 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2211 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 1 = 1 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2212 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 2 = 2 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2213 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 3 = 3 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2214 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 4 = 4 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2215 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 5 = 5 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2216 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 6 = 6 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2217 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 7 = 7 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2218 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 8 = 8 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2219 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 9 = 9 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))).
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details see author's work [34].

4.8 Binomial Coefficients

Binomial coefficients are well known in literature. They are given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m-r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbb{N}.$$

In above subsections, we gave examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, etc. Still, one can have similar kind results using **binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways, digit's order and reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned} 6435 &:= C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) &= C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6) \\ 15504 &:= C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) &= C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\ 42504 &:= C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) &= C(4!, -05 + 24) \\ 54264 &:= C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) &= C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4} + 5)!) \\ 74613 &:= C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) &= C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12650 &:= C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!) & 28 &:= C(8, 2) \\ 12870 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!) & 792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7) \\ 14950 &:= C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!) & 924 &:= C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!) \\ 18564 &:= C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!) & 2024 &:= C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!) \\ 19448 &:= C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8) & 4845 &:= C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4) \\ 26334 &:= C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4}) & 00378 &:= C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!) \\ 43758 &:= C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8) & 00792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!) \\ 53130 &:= C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!). & 00924 &:= C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!)). \end{aligned}$$

Consecutive sequential representations:

$$\begin{aligned} 25920 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 0 & 98280 &:= 0 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25921 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 1 & 98281 &:= 1 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25922 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 2 & 98282 &:= 2 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25923 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 3 & 98283 &:= 3 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25924 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 4 & 98284 &:= 4 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25925 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 5 & 98285 &:= 5 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25926 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 6 & 98286 &:= 6 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25927 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 7 & 98287 &:= 7 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25928 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 8 & 98288 &:= 8 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25929 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 9. & 98289 &:= 9 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}). \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [35].

4.9 S-gonal numbers

The formula for **S-gonal numbers** is given by

$$P(n, s) := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2.$$

This subsection brings some examples of selfie numbrs using **S-gonal numbers**. These examples are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$4992 := P(4!, 9 + 9 + 2)$ $7744 := (P(7, 7) - 4!)^{\sqrt{4}}$ $7896 := 7 \times P(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 6)$ $65485 := -P(6, 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 8^5$ $65943 := P(6, 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})!^4 - 3)$ $67977 := (6 + 7) \times (P(9, 7) + 7!)$ $72495 := -P(7 + 2, 4) + 9!/5$ $83544 := \sqrt{P(8, 3)} \times (5! - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}}.$	$8967 := 7 \times P(P(6, \sqrt{9}), 8)$ $9504 := 4! \times P(\sqrt{0! + 5!}, 9)$ $9744 := 4! \times P(4 \times 7, \sqrt{9})$ $49281 := 1 \times 8! + P(29, 4!)$ $49548 := -8! - P(4!, 5) + 9!/4$ $50424 := 4! \times P(-2 + 4!, \sqrt{0! + 5!})$ $52895 := (5 + P(9, 8))^2 - 5$ $53995 := (5! - P(9, \sqrt{9})) \times 3!! - 5.$
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The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$86640 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 0$ $86641 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 1$ $86642 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 2$ $86643 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 3$ $86644 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 4$ $86645 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 5$ $86646 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 6$ $86647 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 7$ $86648 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 8$ $86649 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 9.$	$5640 := 0 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$ $5641 := 1 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$ $5642 := 2 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$ $5643 := 3 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$ $5644 := 4 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$ $5645 := 5 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$ $5646 := 6 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$ $5647 := 7 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$ $5648 := 8 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$ $5649 := 9 + P(4!, 6) \times 5.$
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For more details refer author's work [29].

4.10 Centered Polygonal Numbers

The formula for **centered polygonal numbers** is given by

$$K(n, t) := \frac{tn(n-1)}{2} + 1, \quad t > 2.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **centered polygonal numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 2883 &:= K(2 \times 8, 8) \times 3 & 01051 &:= K(15, 010) \\
 2888 &:= K(2 + 8, 8) \times 8 \\
 3640 &:= K(3!, 6) \times 40 & 01199 &:= K(9, \sqrt{9}) \times (1 + 10) \\
 14939 &:= -1 + (K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 3) \times 9 & 59938 &:= K(8, 3!) + (\sqrt{9})!! + 9^5 \\
 14959 &:= (-1 + K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 5) \times 9 & 62424 &:= 4! \times K(2 + 4!, 2 + 6) \\
 \\
 15144 &:= K(15, (-1 + 4)!) \times 4! & 63384 &:= 4! + (K(8, 3) + 3) \times 6! \\
 15347 &:= (-1 + 5)! \times 3!! - K(4!, 7) & 63744 &:= 4! \times (K(4!, 7) + 3 + 6!) \\
 15399 &:= K(1 \times 5! / 3!, 9) \times 9 & 63973 &:= K(3! + 7, 9) \times K(3!, 6). \\
 00938 &:= K(\sqrt{K(8, 3!)}, (\sqrt{9})!) \times (0! + 0!)
 \end{aligned}$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 99360 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99361 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99362 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99363 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99364 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99365 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99366 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99367 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99368 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99369 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [29].

4.11 Quadratic-Type Selfies

The formula for **quadratic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^2, n > 0, n \in N.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **quadratic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$48 := -Q(4) + Q(8)$	$49 := Q((-9) + Q(4))$
$81 := Q(8 + 1)$	$89 := Q(9) + 8$
$128 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(8)$	$224 := ((Q(4) - 2) \times Q(Q(2)))$
$292 := Q(Q(Q(2))) + 9 \times Q(2)$	$275 := Q(5) \times (7 + Q(2))$
$322 := Q(Q(3) \times 2) - 2$	$736 := (Q((Q(6) - Q(3))) + (7))$
$1036 := 10^3 + Q(6)$	$0107 := 7 + Q(010)$
$1125 := Q(11 + Q(2)) \times 5$	$0231 := -((Q(13) - Q(20)))$
$1729 := 1 \times 7 \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9)$	$1257 := 7 + Q(Q(5)) \times 2 \times 1$
$9843 := ((Q((-9) + Q(8))) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3$	$2239 := ((-Q(9) + Q((3 \times Q(Q(2)))))) + (Q(Q(2)))$
$10025 := ((100^2) + Q(5))$	$08136 := (Q(6) + Q((Q(3) + ((1 + 80))))))$
$10384 := ((-1) - ((0 - Q(Q(3))) \times (-8))) \times (-Q(4))$	$15323 := (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(Q(2))) + (Q(Q(3)))) \times (Q(5) + 1)))$
$99378 := (9 \times ((Q(93) + Q(Q(7))) - 8))$	$37293 := (-3) + (((Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(2))) - Q(Q(7))) \times Q(3))$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 12680 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12681 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12682 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12683 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12684 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12685 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12686 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12687 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12688 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12689 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [38].

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